

THIRD ITERATION BUSINESS CASE

COORDINATING ACCESS TO HIGH QUALITY MICROORGANISMS AND
ASSOCIATED EXPERTISE FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

A PAN-EUROPEAN DISTRIBUTED RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

For more than a century microbial resources have been recognized as the essential raw material for the advancement of health, and later for biotechnology, agriculture, food technology and for research in the Life Sciences. This has led to the establishment of microbial domain Biological Resource Centres (mBRC) to provide live cultures to foster and support the development of basic and applied science in various European countries. Over recent years a number of initiatives have been undertaken to coordinate access to these resources to present a better offer to Europe and these have created the opportunity for the establishment of a not-for-profit pan-European Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI, www.mirri.org). The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) provides the ideal platform for the development of this infrastructure which takes the interoperability and accessibility of resources and data to a higher level. The current independent, often institutional policies and managed processes will be adapted by partner mBRCs to harmonize holdings, services, the training offer and accession policy and share expertise. Better managed resources coupled with improved interaction with stakeholders will lead to further discovery in all areas of the Life Sciences. Influenced and directed by user needs, the MIRRI Partners will coordinate National Nodes of unparalleled depth and breadth of microbial resources; the infrastructure will improve access to enhanced quality microorganisms in an appropriate legal framework and to resource-associated data in a more interoperable way. The MIRRI Central Coordinating Unit will function as the core of MIRRI established through a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). The National Nodes and national mBRCs will retain their own legal entity but control of some elements of their operations will be transferred to the MIRRI-ERIC. These functions include a proportion of user access to facilities, services and resources; a commitment to take deposits identified in the MIRRI common accession policy and participation in the expert clusters. mBRC participation in the MIRRI National Nodes will be governed by commitments made in the Partner Charter which will include delivery of high quality data to agreed standards, participation in capacity building programmes and a commitment to deliver the MIRRI communication and outreach strategy to stakeholders particularly to bio-industry. MIRRI is putting in place an associate partner scheme to help those wishing to join MIRRI but need assistance in meeting the Partner Charter.

MISSION: THE MIRRI OFFER TO SCIENCE AND BIOINDUSTRY

MIRRI will remove fragmentation in resource and service availability and focus on fundamental needs and challenges and thus will:

- a. facilitate legally protected and regulative compliant access to resources in mBRCs and associated data to maintain a comprehensive supply of biological material in keeping with the demands of the research community;
 - » implement a common acquisition policy to increase capacity and engender trust in order to facilitate access to materials from countries of mega diversity
 - » link member mBRC holdings with contextual data and publicly available data generated on these microorganisms
 - » ensure that key reference strains from publications are available for the furtherance of science;
- b. provide a single access entry point to state-of-the-art microbial biological services and to expert and technical platforms to enable researchers to carry out in-house research on mBRC holdings;
- c. improve the interoperability between mBRCs and overarching, as well as complementary data offers;
- d. implement quality management including standardised procedures, best practices and appropriate tools to increase the quality of the resources collected and their associated data as well as performed services;

- e. establish relationships and with other European research infrastructures and pan-European organisations in related fields;
- f. perform research to add value to strains, match and pool services for public and private institutions and launch joint activities;
- g. provide coordinated external user access to the research infrastructure;
- h. engage the internal researcher and technologist community to implement common standards, share technologies and knowledge and coordinate to resolve operational problems and address user community needs

ADDED VALUE OF MIRRI

Individual mBRCs cannot present global solutions to microbiological needs; this requires a coordinated approach by a consortium of national mBRCs guided by their stakeholders. No single country currently offers a complete coverage of microbial diversity and associated services and therefore an overarching European organisation of the national distributed infrastructures is required to make best use of current capacity, bridge gaps and address the needs of biotechnology today:

- » Economy of scale: **together** MIRRI can afford the full range of often expensive technologies needed to explore biodiversity; offer a more **integrated spectrum** of equipment, data, background knowledge and services
- » **Together** MIRRI provides access to the entire spectrum of microorganisms accessible via a single “entry”-point
- » **Together** MIRRI sets European standards of collection, curation and analysis
- » **Together**, MIRRI sets ambitious, collaborative research goals over extended periods
- » **Together**, MIRRI can share best practices, standards, data and personnel; can exchange personnel for sabbaticals, organize courses together, offer vocational and professional training and education

MIRRI will set the framework for mBRCs to change their operations so that they can underpin and improve the microbiological sciences more effectively and efficiently. This will include the provision of standard strain data sets that will enable users to access the microorganisms’ yet unrecognised potential, deliver regulatory compliance and facilitate knowledge and technology transfer. The mBRC commitments to this is defined more fully in the Partner Charter. Thus they will have impact on the bio-economies of Europe, providing integrated solutions to the Grand Challenges and facilitate the generation of knowledge from data. MIRRI will work with other ESFRI infrastructures providing the essential microbial strain data and expertise to facilitate the use of microorganisms in research and development.

MIRRI will work to counteract the declining basic taxonomic expertise. MIRRI provides coherence in the application of quality standards, homogeneity in data storage and management and sharing of the workload to help release the hidden potential of microorganisms. With its anticipated intense dialogue with users and stakeholders, MIRRI has the potential to add value to research innovation, bring together and foster currently isolated research projects. MIRRI will integrate services and resources, bridging the gap between the organisms and envisaged biotechnological solutions and products in order to enhance competitiveness of Europe’s bio-industry, including the support of SME’s business.

The goal can only be achieved by a distributed research infrastructure with operational units in most, if not all, European Member States. MIRRI will be implemented under an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) which is described in its statutes. The MIRRI-ERIC will implement a work programme as adopted by the General Assembly and provide the common gateway to resources and expertise available in the

individual mBRCs. It will operate on the basis of a central organisation, managed by the Central Coordinating Unit. The user services will be facilitated by the nodes via the collaboration of the respective national stakeholder community. The individual mBRCs maintain their own legal status. The nodes facilitate the respective national stakeholder community, universities, bio-industries, policy makers and scientists to access microbial knowledge. MIRRI invites stakeholders to participate in its further development to meet its objectives.

DRIVING A SUCCESSFUL BIOECONOMY

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) establishes pan-European structures to drive innovation and provide the resources, technologies and services necessary to underpin research thus ensuring improved pathways to discovery for the future (<http://ec.europa.eu/research/esfri/>). The ESFRI strategy recognises the weakness of fragmented individual policies and supports a coherent strategy on research infrastructures in Europe, which facilitates multilateral initiatives and provides Europe with the most up-to-date Research Infrastructures (RI). Science frontiers are evolving and knowledge-based technologies need to be used more widely. MIRRI will integrate services and resources, and encourage innovative solutions providing an integrated solution to microbial resource provision (Figure 1). It will provide coherence in the application of quality standards, homogeneity in data storage and management, and workload sharing to help scientists release the full potential of microorganisms.

Innovation has been placed at the heart of the European Horizon 2020 strategy and is the best means of successfully tackling major global and societal challenges, which are becoming more urgent by the day. There is wide recognition within Europe and beyond that harnessing the full value in biological materials and processes provides the opportunity to create value from new products and services within a more resilient, eco-efficient bio-economy (see, for example, ⁽¹⁾Geoghegan-Quinn, ⁽²⁾The European Commission on the bioeconomy and H2020, ⁽³⁾OECD bioeconomy 2030).

FIGURE 1. COORDINATION AND A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO DATA MANAGEMENT AT THE HEART OF THE MIRRI OFFER

- 1 Geoghegan-Quinn, M., 2010. Commissioner for Research, Innovation and Science, 'Bioeconomy for a better life'. Conference on the Knowledge-based bio-economy towards 2020, Brussels, 14 September.
- 2 http://ec.europa.eu/research/bioeconomy/index_en.htm
- 3 <http://www.oecd.org/futures/long-termtechnologicalsocietalchallenges/thebioeconomyto2030designingapolicyagenda.htm>

Microbiological diversity and well described microbial resources will play a key role in underpinning the bio-economy and driving economic growth through successful biotechnological innovation. Harvesting the full value in such organisms is fundamental to agribusiness, industrial biotechnology health technology, biofuel production and, more fundamentally to new industrial policy and green growth. These are in turn, fundamental to the delivery of continuing European success in a world that is globalising at a startlingly unprecedented pace.

Realizing sustained growth and harnessing a successful bio-economy will not, however, happen spontaneously and will require private and public sectors to work together to develop specific initiatives plus a supportive environment for the bio-economy to emerge. A well-integrated research infrastructure that underpins such efforts will be essential.

IMPACT OF MIRRI ON THE BIO-ECONOMY

Current demand is mainly driven by existing holdings and services. The current MIRRI 13 Partner mBRCs distributed about 198,000 individual resources to users, requested in 109,000 individual orders in the three year period between 2010 and 2012. These were provided equally (50:50) nationally and internationally; 60% of these were shipped to users located in the non-profit sector and 40% to profit making organizations. The global figures for supply from the World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC) affiliate collections are estimated at around 0.5 million per year⁽⁴⁾. The number of microbiologists in both the academic and industrial environment in need of microbial resources is huge and difficult to estimate. These users can be defined as those seeking resources from mBRCs for their research and those requesting deposition of resources into mBRCs. According to wiki.answer.com the number of Universities in Europe is around 400. Adding another 600 research institutes that encompass at least one biological department the total number of European institutes involved in microbiological research would be around 1,000. For SMEs the Annual Report 2013⁽⁵⁾ gives total numbers but does not specify those which are working in the R&D area of microbiology. The MIRRI broader material and extended data offer will engage this larger user community; published estimates demonstrate that mBRCs provide only 1% of the microorganisms used in microbiological research therefore the potential in revealing novel insights in basic as well as applied research is enormous.

The number of resources to be deposited in public mBRCs is likewise difficult to estimate and data are presently available only from a survey performed on microbial holdings financed by the German Research Council. Based upon MIRRI designed 'key strain' criteria about 1,100 strains should be deposited annually in mBRCs to protect public investments. Based on the number of 1,000 European institutes indicated above, about 110,000 microbiological resources should be deposited annually in MIRRI partner mBRCs. Assuming that each of the 36 MIRRI partners and collaborating party mBRCs add an average 400 strains annually to their holdings only about 14,000 of the estimated 110,000 resources (about 13%) worth depositing could be made available annually to the public. In order to make available all novel microbial 'key' resources, each MIRRI member would have to add on average around 2,600 strains to their holdings annually.

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) statistics report that over 4,500 organisms were deposited as part of the publication of patents in 2012⁽⁶⁾. Additionally, it must be noted that microbial resource centres are not the source of all strains on which research is based. The majority of the 20,000 strains cited in 8 European journals on microbiology are not included in mBRC holdings⁽⁷⁾. The European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation Research Infrastructures⁽⁸⁾ estimates that there are around 500,000 life scientists in the research landscape. Many of whom are microbiologists reliant on high quality

4 Smith, D. (2012). Culture Collections. *Advances in Applied Microbiology* 79, 73-118.

5 SME Annual Report 2013 http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/sme/facts-figures-analysis/performance-review/index_en.htm

6 <http://www.wipo.int/ipstats/en/statistics/micros/index.html>

7 Stackebrandt, E. (2010). Diversification and focusing: strategies of microbial culture collections. *Trends in Microbiology* 18, 283-287.

8 Enabling Science EU support to research infrastructures in the life sciences. (2013). European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Directorate B – European Research Area, Unit B.3 – Research Infrastructure

microbial resources. The “bio-economy” as a whole is worth nearly €2 trillion and provides approximately 22 million jobs in Europe alone across sectors as diverse as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, food, chemicals and biofuels⁹. These few facts indicate that the market for strains of microorganisms for MIRRI partner mBRCs is potentially enormous and the potential to improve access to improve the rate of discovery is consequently large. However, mBRCs must be proactive in helping generate new added-value products and services and need a coordinated strategy to be cost effective and efficient. Coordination of access to microbial resources and services will pave the way for innovation in a much more efficient manner than hitherto. At a time of public budget constraints, major demographic changes and increasing global competition there remains too much fragmentation and costly duplication, as well as dangerous gaps, in the European offering. Harnessing the power of networking of collections is essential if efficiency gains are to be realised.

Resources are not currently available in the “right” sort of way – in effect they are “hidden”, both at the level of knowing what resources and first order data are available (so that effort is continuously wasted “reinventing the wheel” through de novo isolation and description of organisms already well understood) and, perhaps more importantly, in translating that data into useable, accessible knowledge that has immediate added value.

There needs to be better interrogation of the full potential of organisms in the field and the ability of potential users to access such knowledge needs to be much more efficient and transparent, with the supply of knowledge and the demand for it being significantly more robustly matched up. In short, the enterprise driving the utilisation of microbial resources in the bioeconomy needs to become demand sensitive and forward looking and exploratory in a way that it has not been for a generation.

MIRRI will provide open access for data and materials generated with public funding establishing clear rights on access and use but where it adds value it may develop tools for which it charges. mBRCs will continue to charge for supply of strains whilst seeking innovative mutually beneficial ways to supply strains into research programmes. Some services will be market driven. MIRRI will work to increase capacity to facilitate acquisition of strains to underpin European life sciences and develop a common accession policy to protect the public investment by funders in developing these resources. MIRRI will work with its members to improve their business plans and expand their private funding. Most importantly a closer relationship will be built with researchers by opening up facilities to enable knowledge and technology transfer providing access to facilities, biological materials and know how to accelerate the discovery processes.

MIRRI ENHANCES THE ROLE OF MICROBIAL DOMAIN BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRES (mBRCs)

For more than a century microbial resources have been recognized as essential raw material for the advancement of basic and applied research in the Life Sciences. The recognition that such resources need to be maintained and made readily available for research led to the establishment of microbial domain resource centres (mBRCs) in most European countries. However, these mBRCs tend to work in isolation, have different funding models and are prone to significant gaps and duplication. A properly networked European system that ensures the interoperability and accessibility of high quality resources and data is essential for the growth of our bio-economy. That same system has to deliver on the vision of a knowledge-based, not just data or materials-based, bio-economy and shine a clear light on the full useable value of our microbial heritage. This is what the pan-European Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) sets out to achieve.

9 EuropaBio (2012) The tax, finance and regulatory framework and global policy comparison. European Commission. <http://www.europabio.org/biotechnology-europe-tax-finance-and-regulatory-framework-and-global-policy-comparison>

THE ROLE OF mBRCs IN MICROBIAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

- » Preservation and supply of biological resources
- » Performance of R&D – adding value
- » Conservation of biodiversity
- » Repositories for protection of intellectual property
- » Enabling the tracking of genetic materials

Microbiological services such as isolation of pure cultures, optimisation of growth conditions, identification of organisms, quality control and environmental sampling

The OECD best practice guidelines for BRCs⁽¹⁰⁾ defines the role of biological resource centres and provides operational details for mBRCs. MIRRI will provide capacity building programmes, share standard operating procedures and provide common solutions to facilitate the transition from traditional culture collection to mBRC. Importantly, through an associate partner scheme, it will coordinate their development, networking and output to better protect and deliver these resources to underpin European research. Currently, Europe faces five fundamental challenges that mean the use of microbial resources in the search for microbial solutions to the grand challenges and in the bio-economy is seriously sub-optimal and thus reduces European competitiveness:

1. FUNDAMENTAL UNCERTAINTY ABOUT THE FULL VALUE INHERENT IN MICROBIAL RESOURCES AND HOW TO ACCESS IT

The idea of releasing the “full value” in microbial resources is pivotal to delivery of the bio-economy. Simply put, such value is the potential for use of microbial resources, as well as the biological systems and components therein, in basic and applied science as well as in innovation (for example, the potential that may be inherent in some fungal metabolites to act as new generation antimicrobials). There is a need to be able to focus the expertise and capacity of mBRCs to provide the specific resources to facilitate discovery of solutions to some of our Grand Challenges such as antimicrobials for control of resistant diseases and accelerate discovery in healthcare. Greater rigour and greater cooperation is required to ensure that research matches industry and societal demand. The broader user community need to be brought into a strategic discussion with MIRRI on addressing such gaps in the short, medium and longer terms.

There remains huge uncertainty about where such untapped value lies and the systems for discovery need to be made much more efficient and productive. mBRCs are both repositories of materials as well as huge amounts of data on microbial system functioning but the integration of systems data with organism taxonomy, functionality and geographical origin (amongst other factors) is at best patchy.

Furthermore, there are large gaps and overlaps in the pool of microbial resources that are described, with concomitant gaps in scientific expertise. In short, prediction and discovery around releasing the full value is very limited, inefficient and often is as hit and miss as the toss of a coin. Key obstacles to research need to be tackled in a co-ordinated way, which in turn will improve the provision of microbial resources beyond what is currently supplied by individual microbial resource collections.

2. MAJOR SHORTCOMINGS IN THE WAY DATA ON MICROBIAL RESOURCES IS PRESENTED.

Addressing the gaps in microbial resources needs to be accompanied by addressing gaps in data about such resources. There currently are significant gaps, both in terms of primary data describing organisms as well as second-order knowledge on their full value (i.e. the potential functions and uses of microbial resources and associated biological systems).

10 OECD (2007). Best Practice Guidelines for Biological Resource Centers (June 2007), http://www.oecd.org/document/36/0,3343,en_2649_34537_38777060_1_1_1_1,00.html

New data needs to be accumulated but before this existing data needs to be used in a more focussed and intelligent way. Ensuring data on microbial strains is interoperable with other data sets allows meta-data analysis and new knowledge generation. Integration of habitat, taxonomic, genomic and phenotypic data can be interrogated smartly to reveal interesting chemistry and utilisable metabolic information in the search for chemical leads. Data accumulation aligned to the needs of potential users will ensure relevance of the microbial resources and facilitate their uptake and use to provide innovative solutions and discover active compounds. A coordinated approach across the mBRCs in the infrastructure will enable the prioritisation of filling data gaps and an obligation of member collections to ensure quality of data and to seek mechanisms to add value will increase the data offer and provide transparency to reveal new uses.

3. THE QUALITY AND REPRODUCIBILITY OF MICROBIAL SCIENCE NEED SIGNIFICANT IMPROVEMENT

It is apparent that Europe depends on strains of uncertain origin for its microbiological research output. Only 194 strains of those cited in the articles of 8 European microbiology journals were sourced or were deposited in public service collections. This implies that 99% of the published literature is based on microbiology that is hard to replicate. The efficiency costs of this are huge, with much published research being difficult or impossible to replicate across laboratories and effective knowledge transfer effectively blocked.

mBRCS are the best place for storage, as the long-term maintenance and distribution of strains are their key functions. It is crucial that public sequence data bases are backed up by making the material on which the sequence was made is available to examine if doubts arise about the data. Additionally, as technologies develop or different areas of the genome need to be sequenced the biological material or at least the DNA must be available. We need to ensure that science has a sound basis and that the correct organisms are used; a backup is needed to ensure biological materials are there for confirmation of results and for exploration of aberrant results ensuring good science.

4. MICROBIAL DIVERSITY SERVICES NEED TO BE TRUSTED AND SUSTAINED

Currently, poor accessibility to microbiological services and gaps in expertise linked to sub-optimal coordination across mBRCs impedes the biotechnologist from getting the help needed in their work. There is a need to deepen and sustain service provision by enhancing microbial science capability and capacity whilst engendering trust in the quality and provenance of such services.

Innovative solutions need to be found to the critical questions for improved mechanisms for delivery of resources and services. The diminishing expertise in the isolation and identification of biodiversity particularly in the switch from traditional taxonomy to the molecular needs to be managed appropriately and the existing expertise coordinated and shared through a common platform. MIRRI will provide the services to access new microbial diversity to allow the biotechnologists to focus on their job to develop the products.

5. THE NEED TO BE ABLE TO CAPTURE VALUE AND BENEFIT FROM MICROBIAL RESOURCES

It is essential that mechanisms for sharing benefits in terms of intellectual property rights, publications, financial rewards etc. are developed if generated from use of microorganism holdings of the partner collections, especially when taking into account the CBD-ABS Nagoya Protocol implications. MIRRI will work towards establishing best practices and keep pace with legislative decision to ensure compliance with European and national law. Additionally, by sharing technologies and enhancing data, MIRRI can help resource holders add value and discover the hidden properties in microorganisms. If this is not recognised then it cannot be released, through characterisation MIRRI can help add value. MIRRI will work towards strategic mutually beneficial access to well described high quality organisms to drive economic growth in bio-businesses. Through such best practices MIRRI can engender trust becoming a technology standards broker and make it easier for reciprocal mutually beneficial exchange of microbial diversity.

IMPACT OF MIRRI ON RESOURCE PROVISION

Underpinning all these challenges is the broader problem of the through-flow of skilled people, perhaps especially in the field of microbial taxonomy, where shortfalls in young talent coming through the training system are beginning to approach what could be a tipping point irretrievable within a generation. MIRRI proposes to answer this problem by bringing together the people we have and develop training and succession plans. The molecular taxonomy skills are in place but the phenotype taxonomy is missing. MIRRI aspires to pool data and integrate it. To add value to the data we need phenotypic taxonomists to make meaningful inputs; the majority of data are outside the collections therefore there is a need to bring this together and add more; MIRRI needs to outreach to data producers and work with them making links to external skills in academia and using them to generate knowledge.

These are a formidable set of challenges to delivery of the benefits of a bio-economy.

No one initiative, no matter how large the investment, can hope to succeed in harvesting all the full value inherent in microorganisms and microbial systems. However, Europe can do much better in terms of how we gather data and turn that into useable knowledge within a developing bio-economy. Efforts can be prioritised and coordinated to address each of the challenges set out above and, together with other existing and developing initiatives, including in the ESFRI space, much increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the bio-economy innovation enterprise, as well as all the downstream economic and social benefits this promises, such as jobs, new business creation and a greener, cleaner and fairer economy.

The proposal presented in the remainder of this document – for the creation of a pan-European Microbial Resources Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) sets out a vision and a way forward to deliver just such improvements in efficient and effectiveness addressing the 5 major challenges articulated here.

THE MIRRI APPROACH

The goal of MIRRI is to create a single infrastructure for microbial resources support for research and development in Europe, where multinational collaboration is currently hampered by the fragmentation of policy, resources and expertise. The creation of MIRRI will be a significant game-changer in terms of elucidating the full value latent in microorganisms and provide a major catalyst to the delivery of a successful bio-economy.

MIRRI will ensure microorganisms and associated data used in value creation are properly characterised, of a quality that can be relied upon and exploited in such a way that delivers fair returns transparently to the origin. This effort will help underpin European jobs and economic growth with a more efficient bio-industry, help us to better access, exchange and understand knowledge on microbial biodiversity, significantly raise the quality and credibility of microbial science and ensure reproducibility of data and better knowledge creation and diffusion.

UNDERLYING PRINCIPLES

The MIRRI model is based on the following founding principles:

- i. MIRRI will operate on the basis of a non-profit entity, established under the European Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC).
- ii. The heart of the MIRRI will be built around an open access infrastructure for handling of and access to expertise, resources and associated data. MIRRI will adhere to the European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures which is in preparation. MIRRI will provide open access for data and materials generated with public funding establishing clear rights on access and use but where it adds value it may develop tools for which it charges. mBRCs will continue to charge for supply of strains. Some services will be market driven and where commercial approaches will be in line with the legal mechanisms establishing MIRRI.
- iii. MIRRI will work to increase capacity to facilitate acquisition of strains to underpin European life sciences and develop a common accession policy to protect the public investment by funders in developing these resources. MIRRI will work with its members to improve their business plans and expand their private funding.
- iv. MIRRI will be open to all European collections that comply with the Rules of Operation and Partner Charter and will help all others meet the requirements.
- v. It will work with Member States to ensure the user community are part of the governance structure to inform its work and output. The infrastructure's expertise will be focussed and enhanced and mechanisms to facilitate its use and to bring in external expertise developed. MIRRI will thus engender trust with its stakeholders and user communities.
- vi. Virtual platforms of expertise will be organised across the infrastructure to share access and costs.
- vii. Duplication of holdings will be kept to a minimum, consistent with the security and diversity of microbial resources. Thus, as part of the MIRRI Preparatory Phase there is planned rationalisation and consolidation of the offerings of current and future MIRRI partner collections. As a result centres of excellence will be established with national funding.
- viii. Collaborations with other ESFRI consortia, e.g., BBMRI-ERIC, ERINHA, EMBRC, ELIXIR, EU-OPEN-SCREEN, Euro-BioImaging, ECRIN, INSTRUCT and ISBE are underway in areas of common interests to

avoid duplication and unproductive competition. These will be augmented where it makes sense by international linkages. Collaboration with other European initiatives will also be explored such as ECDC and QBOL. Managing data interoperability and sharing, where appropriate, expertise in curation and analysis of different types of datasets will bring cost efficiencies and new tools. Access to published datasets will be useful for systems biology and access to expertise in a wide range of computational modelling approaches will enable integrating diverse datasets into quantitative and predictive models. Initially MIRRI will provide its strain metadata that will in return add value to partner data. In order to ensure a manageable start for the implementation of MIRRI, minimal requirements for partner collections will have to be formulated. It is the aim of MIRRI to expand and become an inclusive network where collections are able to improve their level of quality.

- ix. MIRRI will work with partners, to develop joint standards for presenting data and providing services that effectively link phenotypic and genomic data for users. This will add significant value to the ESFRI network and the biological resources held.

The Preparatory Phase project is establishing the stakeholder governance mechanisms and an effective Business Plan to deliver and ensure sustainability. It will aim to secure longer term support for subsequent phases, examining suitable business strategy and revenue lines to reach technical, legal and financial maturity. It will provide the tools, concepts and design to enter the implementation and operational phases.

MIRRI'S STAKEHOLDERS

Key to the success of MIRRI is to manage its stakeholders' expectations and to this end a communication and outreach strategy has been prepared (Figure 2). The stakeholders have been identified, their interest and power to influence MIRRI's development and operations assessed and plans for their involvement are underway.

FIGURE 2. COMMUNICATION WITHIN THE MIRRI ENVIRONMENT

The MIRRI stakeholders have been assigned to the categories Allies, Supporters, Latents and Bystanders each providing and receiving benefits from MIRRI (Table 2.1 and Figure 3). The **Allies** are the most important stakeholder group, having much power to support the project as well as a high interest in it. As a priority group these stakeholders will be involved in discussions and, in specific cases, brought formally into the decision making processes. A second group the **Supporters** have less power to support the project but a substantial interest in it; these stakeholders are being brought into the project through consultation areas of their interest or actively involving them in various outreach tasks. The **Latents** have the power to support the project, but do not seem to be specifically interested in mBRC activities. Therefore activities to raise their interest will be undertaken potentially leading to their shift to become Allies. Finally the **Bystanders** who have neither much interest in the project nor the power to support it; nevertheless, it may be possible to increase their interest in the project, i.e. shift them to the Supporters or at least prevent their adverse effect through misinformation.

STAKEHOLDER	CATEGORY LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT	GOAL OF INTERACTION
Main National Contributor	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Member State signatory to the MIRRI-ERIC, funder of mBRCs and cluster activities
Other National Contributor	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Member State signatory to the MIRRI-ERIC, funder of mBRCs and cluster activities
Industrial User	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	MIRRI and mBRC users; expert advisory panel for CCU; governance role
Academic User	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	MIRRI and mBRC users; expert advisory panel for CCU
Civil Service User	Bystanders, inform	Collaborator on national policy and regulation
National Collections / mBRCs	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Participants in national nodes; MIRRI provider, cluster and project collaborator
National and International Patent Offices, Technology Transfer Units	Allies, collaborate	IP policy advice; Advisory Board; business policy advice
Research Funders	Latents, consult	Cluster activity funders
Research Establishments / Universities	Allies, collaborate	MIRRI and mBRC users; collaborators in cluster activities and projects; advisory; members expert platforms
Depositors	Allies, collaborate	Mind-set change on deposit; collaborators in cluster activities and projects; uptake of deposit incentive programme
Journal Editors	Supporters, involve	Journal policy to encourage deposit of strains
Associations for Training and Education	Supporters, involve	Training programmes; capacity building, Advisory Board
Labour Union, Equal Opportunity Commissioners and Departments	Bystanders, inform	Specialist advice;
Legal, Regulatory and Normative Institutions/Authorities	Allies, collaborate	Policy development; expert panel; Advisory Board
Supra-/International Organisations	Allies, collaborate	Collaborator; networking and outreach; funder; Advisory Board
Media	Bystanders, inform	Publicity and outreach
Governing Board (of MIRRI)	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Direction and advice
Advisory Board (of MIRRI)	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Governance, guidance and expert advice
Biodiversity Associations	Allies, collaborate	Conduit for communication with users
Bio-industry Associations	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Conduit for communication with users
EU/ESFRI	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Funder, Advisory Board
EU Infrastructure / Infrastructure projects	Allies, highly relevant, collaborate	Collaborators; Advisory Board, network partner
Collection-related Associations and Networks	Allies, collaborate	Network partner
Opponents of Biotechnology	Bystanders, inform	Ensure they have the right message and information
Government Commission	Allies, collaborate	MIRRI lobbyist
Regional Resource Infrastructures (outside Europe)	Supporters, involve	Collaborator and network partner

TABLE 2.1. STAKEHOLDERS AND THEIR INTERACTION WITH MIRRI

FIGURE 3: CATEGORISATION OF MIRRI STAKEHOLDERS (1: MAIN NATIONAL CONTRIBUTOR, 2: OTHER NATIONAL CONTRIBUTOR, 3: INDUSTRIAL USER, 4: ACADEMIC USER, 5: CIVIL SERVICE USER, 6: NATIONAL COLLECTIONS/mBRCs, 7: PATENT OFFICES, TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER UNITS, 8: RESEARCH FUNDERS, 9: RESEARCH ESTABLISHMENTS/UNIVERSITIES, 10: DEPOSITORS, 11: JOURNAL PUBLISHER, 12: ASSOCIATIONS FOR TRAINING AND EDUCATION, 13: LABOUR UNION, EQUAL OPPORTUNITY, 14: LEGAL, REGULATORY, NORMATIVE INSTITUTIONS, 15: SUPRA-/INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS, 16: MEDIA, 17: GOVERNING BOARD (OF MIRRI), 18: ADVISORY BOARD (OF MIRRI), 19: BIODIVERSITY ASSOCIATIONS, 20: BIO-INDUSTRY ASSOCIATIONS, 21: EU/ESFRI, 22: EU INFRASTRUCTURE/INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS, 23: COLLECTION-RELATED ASSOCIATIONS & NETWORKS, 24: OPPONENTS OF BIOTECHNOLOGY, 25: GOVERNMENT COMMISSION, 26: REGIONAL RESOURCE INFRASTRUCTURES (OUTSIDE EUROPE))

HOW MIRRI WILL DELIVER

This distributed infrastructure facilitates access to a broader range of high quality microorganisms with added value through associated data to help realise their intrinsic value. The products and services will be delivered through the individual mBRC participants but a MIRRI web portal will bring these offers together and show where products and services can be found. Any individual mBRC can be a contact point but their offer will be enhanced by the cross infrastructure holdings and expertise.

MIRRI will offer something new to science and bio-industry by making a paradigm change in the operations of mBRCs to ensure they underpin and improve the microbiological sciences, make input on bio-economies and provide the resources to discover integrated solutions to the grand challenges and to generate knowledge from data. This will be achieved through coordinated acquisition policy that will broaden the range of resources and increase capacity through more efficient use and expansion of facilities with an improved data offer to facilitate the uptake of microbial resources by biotechnologists and accelerate the process chain to discovery of new active molecules.

MIRRI will improve the quality and reproducibility of microbial science (research) by providing validated reference materials and ensuring key strains from the scientific literature and research upon which the science hypotheses hinge are retained for further use. Current training offers will be expanded to make use of state-of-the-art learning tools, give access to training facilities at various levels (technical, research linked etc.); formal courses and workshops and provide the essential sets of skills to help drive the bio-economy.

THE DATA OFFER (INTEROPERABILITY TO FACILITATE DATA MINING)

MIRRI will connect its data to other relevant data sets to facilitate the generation of knowledge. Following the principles laid down in the report *Riding the wave explaining How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data*⁽¹¹⁾ where the benefits of accelerating the development of a fully functional e-infrastructure for scientific data is described. Interrogating member collections strain data at several levels will enable the identification of potential chemical entities and properties to deliver solutions and indicate where to find them. Utilising phylogenetic hierarchy to extend individual strain data to relatives, or chemistry through host and substrates can lead to a broader range of organisms that have the potential property sought. Additionally, when discoveries are made environments can be identified where more microbial diversity with the property can be found. MIRRI will seek data holding partners and through initiatives of ELIXIR and BioMedBridges will ensure interoperability of its community data to facilitate accelerated discovery and innovation.

There needs to be better interrogation of the hidden value of organisms in the field. Such interrogation should enable exploration, discovery, description and generation of knowledge, not just present the data available. It needs to be:

- » specialised - specific collections in a MIRRI matrix have complementary expertise
- » targeted - collections become economically and scientifically relevant
- » focussed in line with demand and address current and near future needs
- » vision-driven - appropriately forward looking and exploratory

The data offering needs to be clearer. Specifically:

- » databases need to be coordinated across collections
- » integration of data across and between collections
- » implementation of minimum data sets

Datasets across and beyond collections need to exist at different levels. These need to be integrated and then data-mined. They need to address:

- » ecosystem and habitat
- » typical strain properties
- » geographical locations
- » Genebank - strain number - phenotype - downstream properties linkages
- » unambiguous databases of phenotypic properties - e.g. enzymes, metabolites and including chemotaxonomic information
- » phylogenetic hierarchy

A short term target for MIRRI is to identify the databases that it needs to develop or link to and ways to integrate them. By applying data standards and ensuring interoperability in the medium term MIRRI users will have access to a data landscape that can be mined for useful properties. MIRRI's data offering will change

11 European Union (2010). *Riding the wave. How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data*. Final report of the High Level Expert Group on Scientific Data. A submission to the European Commission. Printed by Osmotica.it. http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/itemlongdetail.cfm?item_id=6204

the game on discovery and exploitation by facilitating the identification of the yet to be discovered value of microbial resources.

Partnership will be key to the success of MIRRI's data strategy and MIRRI must learn lessons from the other ESFRI infrastructures and to work with ELIXIR to ensure data interoperability. The data integration and thus value-added needs to be delivered in three steps:

- » Utilise standards for the integration of data within mBRCs according to defined and controlled ontologies; providing a trusted, good and accurate interface. Increase the level of data on the mBRC's own strains from paper information into an electronic format.
- » Collaborate with ELIXIR and other ESFRI databases to mine across databases and begin to deliver economically relevant data. This envisages plugging into investment in Big Data and HPC to add information, thus value into the existing large volumes of data in mBRCs. This is a scientific enterprise – with data mining and integration at its heart. The goal is to offer novel data sets and data combinations to very well informed customers who are then able to use such data sets in creating new knowledge and opportunities.
- » Turning new data into new knowledge and making that knowledge available through integrated and open knowledge networks. Knowledge presents the hidden value in recognisable terms for investment. It envisages the creation of a knowledge collaboration based on data networking. It is the gold standard of a publicly-funded shared knowledge it integrates MIRRI metadata with for example, EU-OPENSOURCE in a way that casts light on G8 aspirations for new antimicrobials. Thus - data path-finding will drive the engine of MIRRI.

LEGAL CERTAINTY ON USE

MIRRI follows the globally accepted principles of establishment of Biological Resource Centres that not only retain resources and information of high quality but make them available in a legally compliant operational framework. MIRRI will work with resource providers, policy makers and users to provide legal clarity of rights in use and transparency to engender trust. Additionally, MIRRI Partners have established codes of practice, specifically in biosecurity to reduce potential mal intended use. MIRRI will work to provide resources in a safe and compliant way.

The implementation of the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing⁽¹²⁾ requires regulatory compliance as well as due diligence in sourcing and seeking legal clarity in use. The Protocol also requires an environment of monitoring and reporting on access and use of genetic resources. Specifically MIRRI will ensure capture of value and benefit to places of origin with respect to their holdings; member mBRCs will follow codes of practice that will facilitate transparency in legality of access and transfer of rights to utilise according to the Mutually Agreed Terms (MAT) and Prior Informed Consent (PIC).

BUSINESS MODELS FOR OPERATIONS

MIRRI recognises the need of biotechnology industry to keep ahead of its competitors in business and thus the need for confidentiality in sourcing organisms and exchanging information. MIRRI will make available coordinated platforms of resources, tools, data and expertise through controlled and confidential business models. Each individual microbial resource centre will be a point of contact for industry to do business with MIRRI. Thus a company's most appropriate mBRC will not only bring its range of products and services but if needed will have the wealth of 400,000 plus microorganisms and the expertise across the member collections behind it.

12 Text of the Nagoya Protocol <http://www.cbd.int/abs/text/default.shtml>

BROADER ACCESS TO MATERIALS

Having set up its data offer to identify new sources of lead compounds, provided legal certainty of use and appropriate business models MIRRI can reach out to regional and global efforts facilitating access to global resources. Engendered trust, compliant delivery and opportunity to track the use of overseas genetic resources can facilitate access to materials from countries of mega diversity for global science and discovery.

SECURITY OF STRAINS FOR FUTURE USE AND PROTECTION OF PUBLIC FUNDING INVESTMENT

It is clear that scientists do not currently source research strains and deposit their biological materials in public service microbial resource centres. MIRRI wants to change this and will work with journal editors, research funders and scientists to offer incentive for change. It is absolutely essential that if science, particularly microbiology, is to impact on global challenges and the bio-economy that microbial resource centres need to work together with all stakeholders to achieve this. Improved quality resources with enhanced knowledge from data provided by these centres will make a difference.

BETTER RESOURCES AND SERVICES TO MEET STAKEHOLDER NEEDS

MIRRI will work with its partners to establish improved management of microbial resources to provide coordinated access to high quality resources. Working with stakeholders to achieve common strategies in acquisition, characterisation and delivery the MIRRI Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure will deliver high quality and protect public investment in the collection and generation of information on microbiological material. MIRRI will deliver efficiency with a common acquisition policy for cultures to increase holdings selectively for more targeted exploitation and to provide a deeper understanding of microbial diversity at the genetic and epigenetic levels and their function in the environment to address global challenges, adding value through characterisation and generating data and delivering capacity to house strains.

Improving transparency, in access and demand/ supply side integration; resources are not currently available in a straight forward and coordinated way – in effect they are “hidden”

- » traditional collections are not up to date with current user demands – they are not “new” BRCs as defined by the OECD
- » BRCs need new innovative activities that are well perceived externally
- » the properties of unique strains need to be understood and delivered better
- » information needs to be available to help people target the right resources for the specific use in mind
- » a virtuous handshake needs to be struck between the supply and demand for collections and vice versa. This currently arguably is absent and needs to be at the heart of the MIRRI enterprise
- » facilitate links to industry in a timely and appropriate manner
- » build a stakeholder community and incorporate this group in the Governance structure
- » develop communication targets and channels including a stakeholder forum
- » encourage and incentivise the scientist to use mBRCs through improving trust, transparency and mutual collaboration

The MIRRI Preparatory Phase is preparing the strategies and structure to deliver these improvements to the European Research Area. The latter includes appropriate governance, management, statutes and a Partner Charter.

PARTICIPATION, MANAGEMENT, GOVERNANCE AND CONSTRUCTION

The MIRRI infrastructure itself including its governance structure is being refined during the Preparatory Phase. It will be established under the European Research Infrastructure Consortium⁽¹³⁾ agreement as a distributed model with a Central Coordinating Unit (CCU) as the operational centre. The MIRRI-ERIC statutes set out the main provisions for the governance and management of the MIRRI-ERIC and its services, activities and operations; the detail of the implementation of the statutes is provided in the Rules of Operation. Figure 4 provides the membership components defined in Article 9(1) of Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009. Consequently the membership of MIRRI-ERIC is open to Member States, Associated Countries, Third Countries other than Associated Countries and Intergovernmental Organisations for an initial minimum term of 3 years.

FIGURE 4. MIRRI BUILT USING THE ERIC STRUCTURE

The work programme of MIRRI will be delivered through clusters of experts who will be sourced from both within and outside the RI. Each Member State will establish a National Node to coordinate country activities. Partners beyond Europe will ensure global participation and applicability of outputs. The current iteration of the MIRRI structure is outlined below and is based on models that are already available from other ESFRI consortia that ensure good governance and control.

The MIRRI-ERIC will include some coordinated activities formerly part of the individual mBRC functions. These elements will include a proportion of user access to facilities, services and resources; a commitment to take deposits identified in the MIRRI common accession policy and participation in the expert clusters.

STRUCTURE

European Member States will be invited to sign the MIRRI-ERIC along with EU Associated Countries, Third Countries or Intergovernmental Organizations and thus accept the MIRRI-ERIC Statutes. All can participate either as Full Members or Observers. The legal minimum number of ERIC signatures from Member States

13 European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) http://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index_en.cfm?pg=eric

to construct the infrastructure is three although the critical mass to provide financial stability may well be 5 members (see Financial Plan below and Annexe IV). The main obligations of Member States are to send a representative to the MIRRI General Assembly to provide direction in delivery of appropriate outputs and to provide funding aimed at developing capacity and quality at the national level. The three main elements of the MIRRI structure are the Central Coordinating Unit, the Governing Board and the General Assembly (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5. MIRRI-ERIC GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

The MIRRI-ERIC will be steered at a number of levels (see figure 6) the decisions and direction from the General Assembly at the governing level needs to be translated in action and delivered. This will be carried out at the management level under advice of the Advisory Bodies and executed by the CCU.

FIGURE 6. MIRRI-ERIC STEERING LEVELS

Members would contribute to the MIRRI-ERIC budget paying a fee that is yet to be finalised but see estimates made in the Financial Plan and in Annexe IV. Each Member State must appoint a National Node (NN) and one National Coordinator who is responsible for the country to follow the General Assembly's policies. These National Coordinators come together to form the National Coordinator's Forum who appoint a chair to sit on the Governing Board. Up to two experts (one of which should be the National Coordinator) can accompany the Member State representative in the meetings. Each Member State signing the MIRRI-ERIC has one vote, influencing the development of strategies and policies. They also have priority rights from their stakeholders to access the infrastructure services and the possibility to participate in Union project proposals addressed to RIs. Observing Members in general will be countries in the process of developing appropriate partner facilities or countries or intergovernmental organisations involved in joint projects. They participate in the General Assembly but without voting rights, their national stakeholders can apply for access to the Infrastructure services and expertise with priority over non-members to help them establish National Nodes and become full participants in the MIRRI-ERIC.

The National Nodes (NNs) will bring together the partners (national mBRCs, experts and service providers) that meet the MIRRI requirements presented in the Partner Charter. The user will have access to strains available in Member NNs as well as directories of other services, thematic clusters, facilities, expertise, data etc. via direct contact with mBRCs, National Nodes or the MIRRI portal. These services will be delivered directly from the providing institutions (mBRCs) belonging to MIRRI, which will maintain the possibility of providing services outside MIRRI. The NNs will coordinate the activities of the partners within the country, to organise funding, to provide or to advise in training issues, to enhance the development of the national mBRCs as well as to expand the national network to improve the MIRRI offer.

COMPOSITION OF THE GOVERNING, OPERATIONAL AND EXECUTIVE BODIES

The decision making body of the MIRRI-ERIC will be the General Assembly which is composed of representatives from all Members. As indicated above only Members have voting rights. Observers can contribute by expressing their opinion and can, through their participation in the General Assembly, be informed about all decisions taken by this body. It will meet at least once a year; amongst its responsibilities are to appoint the Executive Director, confirm the Executive Officers of the Governing Board, appoint the Advisory Board, decide on strategies for the construction and maintenance of MIRRI, approve the work programme and annual budget of MIRRI-ERIC. The General Assembly also approves the Rules of Operation, sets the annual fee for Members and Observers, approves annual reports and accounts of MIRRI-ERIC and approves admission of new Members and Observers. The General Assembly elects a President and a Vice President.

The Advisory Board shall advise the General Assembly on strategic issues, operation, development, services, etc. The Executive Director will be the responsible to execute all decisions taken by the Assembly helped by the Central Coordinating Unit (CCU).

GOVERNING BOARD

The Governing Board, appointed by the General Assembly, together with the Executive Director form the executive body of the MIRRI-ERIC (Figure 7). The Executive Director is the Chair of the Governing Board. The General Assembly appoint the Vice Chair. The Governing Board establishes the Rules of Operation for the MIRRI-ERIC. It is responsible for its operation and implementation of the Work Programme. It follows General Assembly' directions and decisions under the guidance of the Advisory Board which may have ethical, scientific, legal and industrial expertise. The activities of MIRRI-ERIC are periodically evaluated by an independent Advisory Board.

FIGURE 7. GOVERNING BOARD

CENTRAL COORDINATING UNIT (CCU)

The Executive Director is the legal representative of MIRRI-ERIC, administrator of the MIRRI-ERIC and leader of the Central Coordinating Unit (CCU), recommending the appointment of its staff to the Governing Board. The CCU provides the administration and support services for the general management and administration of the MIRRI-ERIC, is the central point for communication with stakeholders and is responsible for the promotion of the infrastructure. It will be established in one of the EU-Member States signing the MIRRI-ERIC as agreed by the founding Members of the infrastructure.

The CCU will comprise a management office with appropriate staffing. The expertise will include IT Management, a Communication/Customer Relations, Quality Management System expertise and a Secretary. Other skills (Figure 8) will be required to carry out the extended functions of the CCU as it moves into its Implementation Phase including legal and regulatory guidance and support, business development, fund raising, marketing, training, education and technology use and development. The functions of the CCU will include:

- » general management of the ERIC, guided by the Governing Board
- » prepare policies and strategies for approval by the Governing Board
- » handle external user access to the MIRRI Research Infrastructure, preferentially on a collaborative basis with in-house researchers including handling finances related to access
- » collaborative project development and management, coordinating the infrastructure with other international initiatives in collaboration with the National Coordinators
- » marketing and publicity
- » assist shared capacity building, training and education,
- » assist in Knowledge and Technology Transfer to SMEs and industry
- » managing the technical aspects of mBRCs in collaboration with the National Coordinators
- » providing an intergovernmental forum on mBRC issues
- » technical issues for membership

The CCU will be responsible for ensuring collaboration and appropriate linkages with stakeholders and in particular related networks and project consortia. At present, many mBRCs are members of international associations such as the European Culture Collections' Organization (ECCO), the World Federation of Culture Collections (WFCC), the World Data Centre for Microorganisms (WDCM), the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the Genomic Encyclopedia of Bacteria and Archaea (GEBA), etc. which promote the global integration of microbial biodiversity. Other types of networks such as microbial scientific associations, the European Federation of Biotechnology (EFB) or the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) may help in targeted (academic / bio-industry) MIRRI outreach.

Connections with other closely related ESFRI projects (EU-OPENSREEN, EMBRC or ELIXIR, ISBE, ERINHA, EMTRAIN) have been established and others are being evaluated to determine potential common services. Some have been identified for proposals for Horizon 2020 calls.

FIGURE 8. MIRRI-ERIC CENTRAL COORDINATING UNIT

A host country will be selected for the CCU. The MIRRI-ERIC will establish a statutory seat and a procedure to aid the process of locating it. There are a number of options to be considered in ensuring these functions can be carried out involving out sourcing, Liaison Officers at each partner for managing practical issues with the CCU but all activities would be under the direction of the MIRRI Executive Director. The Preparatory Phase offers an opportunity for partners to explore with Member States, the willingness and practicalities to host the statutory seat and consequently where the CCU will be located. The process will be one based on open bidding anticipating that the bidder will specify what they offer (staffing, housing, secondary support and sustained financing of the CCU) and some secondary conditions (easy to reach, academic and innovative environment, nearby meeting facilities, etc.). The call will be to all EU Member States and resulting bids will be prioritised by an independent advisor. After proposers have had the opportunity to revise their proposals Member States party to the MIRRI-ERIC at an General Assembly will select the favoured proposal.

The operational structure of the MIRRI-ERIC will be a distributed model with a hub and spokes design connecting the CCU to the NNs bringing together the national partners (mBRCs, experts and service providers) that

meet the MIRRI requirements. Access to the MIRRI offer will be via a virtual portal, directly via mBRCs or their national nodes (NNs) see Figure 7.

THE NATIONAL NODES (NNS)

The NN can be at a single national mBRC or be a National Network represented by a legal entity appointed by the Member State. The mBRCs in the NN will sign up to the MIRRI Partner Charter that will include criteria and specific commitments to data provision and policy adherence. The NN will help network members achieve these criteria and to meet the national needs. NNs will contribute with resources, data, expertise and services to functional transnational expert clusters brought together to solve infrastructure problems and European research community needs and challenges. Each NN will have a coordinator who would accompany the Member State representative at the MIRRI General Assembly.

The National Coordinator will act as the main liaison between the MIRRI-ERIC and the National Node. National Coordinators are responsible for their country to follow the General Assembly' policies and strategies for the development and exploitation of the research infrastructure. A National Coordinators' Forum of all National Coordinators will be established to ensure the implementation of the strategies laid out by the General Assembly. The forum has to maintain coherence and consistency across the distributed infrastructure and collaboration between National Nodes.

FIGURE 9. GENERATION OF ANNUAL MIRRI WORKING PLAN

CLUSTERS OF EXPERTISE

The clusters of expertise will be the main functional unit to carry out the work programme agreed by the General Assembly (figure 9). They can be brought together on an ad-hoc basis responding to concrete demands and can be of short or long-term duration. There are several that constitute the pillars of MIRRI and, as such, will be assembled from the beginning. These may include:

- » Legal issues concerning the handling, delivery and use of microbial resources. This cluster will help both users and providers to comply with biosafety, biosecurity, IPR and ABS regulations.
- » Taxonomic platforms of experts and technologies that can support both mBRCs and the user community in identification, authentication and selection of strains.
- » Application-driven, providing an opportunity for experts to be brought together for example to provide microbial solutions in food security or healthcare or help a user address a specific need, a technological problem or source the most appropriate organisms for a specific property.

- » Further develop preservation technology to broaden the range of organisms stored improving reliability and reproducibility.
- » Quality management.
- » Data management and delivery.
- » New technologies application and coordination of use.

Transnational clusters to address issues such as coverage of quarantine reference materials, perform geno- and phenotyping of resources or provide expertise at different levels (particular taxa or environment, methods, etc.) are foreseen. Harnessing existing projects and networks can be the basis to harmonize or develop these kinds of clusters.

PARTNER CHARTER

Membership in MIRRI-ERIC, at both Member (the Member States etc.) and Partner level (NNs and mBRCs), does not influence any activity outside the MIRRI-ERIC statutes. The Partner Charter defines criteria that are to be met by the partners and criteria for resource and service providers (mBRCs) as follows:

- i. Must demonstrate satisfactorily to the General Assembly the implementation of a **quality management system (QMS)** following the principles of the **OECD Best Practice Guidelines for mBRCs** (criteria will set and assessed via the QMS cluster; partners will be accepted via the General Assembly).
- ii. Commit themselves to be, at any time, **transparent** to customers. Partners will clearly indicate which services and collection components are part of the MIRRI consortium, and as such are guaranteed by MIRRI quality standards.
- iii. Guarantee **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)** access to microbial resources they bring to MIRRI by complying with the general requirements of MIRRI.
- iv. Commit themselves to implement the **MIRRI policy** in compliance with the **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)**.
- v. Commit themselves to implement **biorisk assessment and biosecurity** measures as described in the ERIC statutes.
- vi. Agree to design (through the Heads of Collections forum), contribute to and implement a **common accession policy** that is based on broadening the range of strains available, reducing duplication and increasing capacity.
- vii. Commit themselves to develop a **sustainability strategy** to ensure that their MIRRI holdings and services remain available for the consortium.
- viii. Commit themselves to **provision of data and information** to meet MIRRI's data management and delivery need.
- ix. Commit themselves to **participation in applicable cluster activities** and implement resulting harmonised practices, strategies and policies.
- x. Actively seek **bio-industry interaction** and responding to advice.
- xi. Exceptions regarding the membership criteria can be established but have to follow transparent decision-making procedures and be approved by the General Assembly.

A mechanism will be defined for achieving membership status (see figure 10). Members will need to comply with the Partner Charter and expected to reach good levels of compliance management.

FIGURE 10. ASSIGNMENT PROCESS FOR MIRRI PARTNERS

MIRRI-ERIC ADVISORY BODIES AND ADVISORY BOARD

FIGURE 11. MIRRI-ERIC ADVISORY BODIES AND ADVISORY BOARD

A sound operational framework for MIRRI is crucial for compliance with community best practices in business operation, the legal environment, access to resources delivery and communication to its stakeholders. A strong panel of advisory bodies is needed to keep pace with the ever changing environment and as checkpoints for performance (see figure 11).

These bodies will not only impact on the governance of the MIRRI-ERIC but their advice will be valuable for the National Nodes and partner mBRCs. The relationship between the nodes and the CCU will be critical. The National Nodes will coordinate outputs at the national level with the major services of biological resources and data directly accessed at the mBRC (figure 12).

FIGURE 12. PARTNERS AND OFFERS IN MIRRI-ERIC NATIONAL NODE

The Governance structure will be tested over the final year of the Preparatory Phase of MIRRI. Its impact on the business planning and especially the costs of the operation will be taken into account for the implementation phase. Processes for financial control are being developed, with the current estimations of costs and the sources of revenue, these are outlined in the next section, the financial plan.

SUMMARY

The MIRRI Statutes present the different bodies of the governance structure, defining their responsibilities and the interdependencies between them as well as the decision-making process of the research infrastructure. MIRRI will implement a Work Program as adopted by the General Assembly (Article 3) MIRRI-ERIC Member States will be bound by the statutes and the National Nodes and constituent mBRCs by the Rules of Operation and Partner Charter content. The General Assembly will be the decision-making body of MIRRI-ERIC and will decide on strategies for the construction, maintenance and development of MIRRI; approve the work program and annual budget of MIRRI-ERIC; approve the Rules of Operation and any amendments to the Rules of Operation; approve annual reports on work achieved. The Executive Director through the Central Coordinating Unit will implement the decisions and programs adopted by the General Assembly and submit the annual activity report. The Governing Board will be responsible for the operation of MIRRI-ERIC following the General Assembly directions and decisions, as well as the counsel from the Advisory Bodies. The National Coordinators Forum consisting of all National/Organisational Coordinators will implement the directions and decisions taken by the General Assembly, as well as the counsel from the Advisory Board, at the level of the Members and their national institutions. The work programme will address the coordinated aspects managed by the MIRRI-ERIC. The National Nodes and national mBRCs retain their own legal entity but the control of some elements of their activities is transferred to the MIRRI-ERIC according to the MIRRI-ERIC Statutes.

PROPOSED FINANCIAL PLAN

The MIRRI approach assumes a not-for-profit entity that is sustained by a mixed funding model implying long term core support by participating Member States and income generation by the MIRRI Partners, some through centrally coordinated activities. The balance between core support and income generation is projected to evolve as the consortium is constructed and as operations (including income generation) come on stream. There are two distinct cost centres, the MIRRI-ERIC implemented by the Central Coordinating Unit (CCU) and the second around National Nodes (NNs) and their networked mBRCs.

At present it is only possible to provide broad projections of likely costs and expected revenues, based on the structural and operating assumptions set out elsewhere in this paper. These projections will certainly evolve as the design phase of the MIRRI project progresses and as the detail of the proposed consortium is agreed amongst prospective partners.

The coordination of activities such as accession policy, joint business development activities, coordinated services and products will increase effectiveness and lead to cost savings at the mBRC and at the national level.

THE FINANCIAL PLAN FOR THE MIRRI-ERIC AND THE CENTRAL COORDINATING UNIT (CCU)

The costs and revenue lines for the CCU can be estimated more accurately than the variable costs of national nodes at different stages in their development. Table 4.1 summarises both the costs and the project income for MIRRI. Costs include the personnel associated with the CCU, its operational costs and accommodation and consumable costs for the office, data storage, maintenance and use, governance, communication, cluster operation and access. These costs total almost €6.2 million. Income from sources including Member State contributions to the MIRRI-ERIC, partner mBRC fees, third party grants, income from access to facilities, data and expertise and CCU host country contributions is anticipated at around €6.9 million providing a small surplus for investment. The Member State contributions are calculated on the basis of country GDP (see detailed calculations in Annexe IV). The CCU will assume administration of the implementation of the MIRRI-ERIC statutes, provide a single electronic portal or gateway to resources, coordinate the MIRRI quality management and regulatory compliance policy, coordinate expert platforms, bring together project consortia, prepare proposals to answer specific research infrastructure calls, coordinate access to facilities for researchers and coordinate of accession policy for deposit of strains.

The costs have been estimated for these activities. At this Preparatory Phase, these expected expenditures are conceived as the establishment and operation of the MIRRI core services, such as provision of a secretariat for governance and oversight functions, provision and operation of central data services and general support for the operation of the network aspects of the MIRRI consortium. The tasks are limited to coordinating access to data and facilities with a low level of development thus costs have been minimised.

	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	TOTAL
Membership fees	949,984.87 €	922,668.70 €	1,034,756.81 €	1,037,468.28 €	1,037,468.28 €	4,982,346.94 €
Observer fees	76,073.10 €	103,389.27 €	96,518.04 €	42,276.19 €	49,776.19 €	368,032.79 €
Partner fees mBRCs	25,000.00 €	30,000.00 €	35,000.00 €	45,000.00 €	60,000.00 €	195,000.00 €
Partner fees other partners	5,000.00 €	7,000.00 €	9,000.00 €	12,000.00 €	15,000.00 €	48,000.00 €
Third party grants	24,000.00 €	49,000.00 €	69,000.00 €	69,000.00 €	69,000.00 €	280,000.00 €

PROPOSED FINANCIAL PLAN

	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	TOTAL
Cost allowance host country	171,000.00 €	182,925.00 €	195,717.38 €	209,441.37 €	224,493.83 €	983,577.58 €
Income data access and expert clusters	- €	2,000.00 €	5,500.00 €	9,000.00 €	16,000.00 €	32,500.00 €
TOTAL Income	1,251,057.97 €	1,296,982.97 €	1,445,492.22 €	1,424,185.84 €	1,471,738.30 €	6,856,957.30 €
CCU infrastructure costs - host country						
Accommodation	20,000.00 €	20,600.00 €	21,218.00 €	21,854.54 €	22,837.99 €	106,510.53 €
Running costs	11,000.00 €	11,825.00 €	12,711.88 €	13,665.27 €	14,690.16 €	63,892.30 €
Communication and Outreach	40,000.00 €	43,000.00 €	46,225.00 €	49,691.88 €	53,418.77 €	232,335.64 €
Annual meeting, stakeholder meeting	100,000.00 €	107,500.00 €	115,562.50 €	124,229.69 €	133,546.91 €	580,839.10 €
CCU infrastructure costs						
Advice	30,000.00 €	32,250.00 €	34,668.75 €	37,268.91 €	40,064.07 €	174,251.73 €
Advisory Board	20,000.00 €	21,500.00 €	23,112.50 €	24,845.94 €	26,709.38 €	116,167.82 €
Travel and accommodation	140,000.00 €	150,500.00 €	161,787.50 €	173,921.56 €	186,965.68 €	813,174.74 €
IT knot	50,000.00 €	53,750.00 €	57,781.25 €	62,114.84 €	66,773.46 €	290,419.55 €
Expert platforms	100,000.00 €	107,500.00 €	115,562.50 €	124,229.69 €	133,546.91 €	580,839.10 €
CCU costs for personnel						
Director	152,400.00 €	156,972.00 €	161,681.16 €	166,531.59 €	171,527.54 €	809,112.30 €
Secretary	63,500.00 €	65,405.00 €	67,367.15 €	69,388.16 €	71,469.81 €	337,130.12 €
IT Manager	127,000.00 €	130,810.00 €	134,734.30 €	138,776.33 €	142,939.62 €	674,260.25 €
Communication, public relation	82,550.00 €	85,026.50 €	87,577.30 €	90,204.61 €	92,910.75 €	438,269.16 €
Compliance Officer - legal, QMS	127,000.00 €	130,810.00 €	134,734.30 €	138,776.33 €	142,939.62 €	674,260.25 €
Business development, grants	- €	- €	- €	- €	127,000.00 €	127,000.00 €
Technology Transfer Officer	- €	- €	- €	- €	82,550.00 €	82,550.00 €
Training and education	- €	- €	- €	- €	76,200.00 €	76,200.00 €
TOTAL expenses CCU	1,063,450.00 €	1,117,448.50 €	1,174,724.08 €	1,235,499.34 €	1,586,090.68 €	6,177,212.60 €
Over/underfunding	187,607.97 €	179,534.47 €	270,768.14 €	188,686.50 €	-114,352.38 €	712,244.70 €
Account balance previous year	- €	187,607.97 €	367,142.44 €	637,910.58 €	826,597.08 €	2,019,258.07 €

TABLE 4.1 INVESTMENTS AND COSTS FOR THE MIRRI-ERIC CENTRAL COORDINATING UNIT AND ITS OPERATIONS

CCU STAFFING

The envisaged responsibilities and activities are substantial and staffing levels (Figure 8 above) and quality and experience must match. The initial five posts include an Executive Director, Secretary, IT Manager, Communication and Public Relations Officer and Compliance Officer responsible for the legal framework and quality management system. These posts run from year 1. The remaining posts of Business Development Officer, Technology and Knowledge Transfer Officer and Training and Education Officer start in year 5. The duties of the latter posts will be absorbed by the initial staff over the first 4 years.

CCU OPERATIONS

Staff are allocated to tasks to direct the CCU outputs and coordinate the activities identified in the section above on structure. The costs can be split into three areas:

- (1) CCU Infrastructure costs (covered by the host country) which include accommodation, running costs, communication and outreach, project and stakeholder meetings
- (2) CCU operations including advisory roles and bodies, travel and accommodation, IT node and expert platforms
- (3) CCU personnel

Currently these costs are estimated at €6.2 million over the first 5 years for operating the MIRRI-ERIC with most costs being attributed to the key elements of data delivery to facilitate uptake of the microbial resources, giving access to expert platforms and user access to research facilities and resources. It is also possible that some of the costs would be covered by the CCU Host Member State.

The detail on how these costs would be distributed to member states is found in Annex IV. It could be anticipated that the host country would cover the CCU costs outlined in 1) above whereas the salaries will be funded through the MIRRI-ERIC and shared by Member States (figure 13).

FIGURE 13. FINANCING / INCOME SOURCES FOR THE MIRRI-ERIC

NATIONAL NODES AND mBRC DEVELOPMENT AND PARTICIPATION

The costs for establishment and operation of National Nodes (NNs) and the enhancement and participation of the national mBRCs that are directly affiliated with them are much more difficult to assess. The node-specific expenditure is dependent upon a number of factors including the total number of mBRCs participating, the degree of development and maturation of the node, the extent to which mBRCs have devolved some of their activities to a central unit and local costs. The funding of the mBRCs and the NNs is a national obligation outside the costings for the MIRRI-ERIC and to a great extent depends on the level of involvement of national funders. This varies from country to country but is considered an essential part of mBRC business model

as perceived by the OECD. However, MIRRI is keen to support nations in their funding activities as MIRRI services and outputs are dependent on mBRC sustainability and activity. A key element of MIRRI activity is to help mBRCs and their National Nodes develop sound business plans and the content of this section of the business case makes some suggestions and offers models in this regard. Additionally, we need to facilitate the process of inclusion of culture collections in country that wish to join. The Associate Member status will be given to such partners that can deliver resources but need some time and investment to meet the Partner Charter. Such costs are estimated in Annexe IV but participation in MIRRI will make this efficient and more cost effective with potential of sharing solutions and activities to reduce such costs.

COSTS AT THE mBRC LEVEL

Some initial attempts at estimating costs based upon previous project activities and experience of the MIRRI partners have been made in Annexe IV. Costs include those incurred by mBRCs to meet the Partner Charter and those associated with the demands upon them from the MIRRI-ERIC. The MIRRI Partner Charter requires the implementation of best practices, technology development and strengthening of mBRC expertise. Currently most mBRCs that are partner to the MIRRI Preparatory Phase have already invested and reached (or are close to) the required level of performance. They may have costs associated with implementing the common accession policy for which it is estimated that an additional 10% in strain numbers that may add costs around €15.4K. This is not an accurate assessment of cost as some cells are much more difficult to handle and may cost more. These mBRCs have formal quality management systems but if these are not in place then they will require investment here estimated at €12K in year 1 increasing annually for the first 5 years with on running costs of €8K per year totalling just over €116K. However, this is dependent on the size of the collection and in the case of a small one housing 3 or 4 thousand strains may be less than €20K. There may be a need for technology development and human resource development but these costs would reduce in time. Again these costs depend upon the developmental stage the mBRC is at, for example for most of the MIRRI Preparatory Phase Partners these costs will be negligible. In the extreme case all elements may well be needed costing in excess of €612K over the first 5 years. MIRRI introduces the associate partner for those who wish to become partners and have plans to implement the requirements of the Partner Charter; this will help reduce such costs by sharing workload, knowledge and technologies.

Costs at the level of the MIRRI-ERIC concern the collection expansion to increase capacity for strains allocated via the common accession policy; participation in expert platforms and the delivery of transnational access to facilities and resources. These costs do not reflect mBRC full costs only those additional costs of participating in the MIRRI-ERIC. Cost efficiencies, opportunities to participate in funded activities and support in development give partner mBRCs incentive and advantage to join MIRRI. The costs associated with accession of additional strains (€385/strain) include staff costs, consumables and all facility costs to incorporate them into the mBRC. A key function of research infrastructures is to give access to the facilities and resources inside it. Therefore transnational access to researchers is expected and some will be given free to users but funded centrally. Not all access costs will be covered by central funds it is the norm that 20% of these are covered.

Cost estimates are averaged across country boundaries and do not take into account the different organisms and the level of complication of handling some of them and the extent to which some collections characterise strains. Nevertheless, there is solid methodology to these estimates. In order to upgrade mBRCs to reach the operational requirement level, for example implementing OECD best practice and expanding capacity to authenticate and store additional holdings, they will need, to varying degrees, depending on their current level of development, to establish a quality management system. Work in the GBRCN⁽¹⁴⁾ and EMbaRC projects demonstrated that these costs vary depending on the size of the operation and type of quality management system that is implemented. There are additional recurrent (staff) costs to maintain the quality system. The National Nodes will also have one-off constructional and development costs and recurring operational costs.

14 Fritze, D., Martin, D. & Smith, D. (2012). Final report on the GBRCN Demonstration Project. Germany: GBRCN Secretariat. ISBN 978-3-00-038121-8.

Generally it is anticipated that costs will tail off and that long term activities need to be supported by the individual mBRC budgets supported by improved revenue lines and institutional and government funding where appropriate. In large part, the measure of the success of MIRRI will be the breadth and depth of these activities and the extent to which revenue generation for them can be channelled to augment further developments.

COSTS AT THE NATIONAL NODE LEVEL

There are very few national organisations of mBRCs in Europe that function in any way near to that expected in MIRRI. The Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms (BCCM™) is well supported by the Belgian Science and Policy Office both financially and in direction. This can serve as a model. In other countries there are some more loose federations of collections but these tend to operate more on the level of scientific associations and there is little mandate to impact on institutional policy. MIRRI would anticipate that at the very least the NN would be able to ensure that mBRCs implemented the Partner Charter and were able to ensure commitments made through the MIRRI-ERIC Statutes were implemented. There are single national collections in some countries so we can also anticipate single mBRCs representing the NNs too.

It is proposed that the MIRRI consortium operates under a mixed model whereby Member States provide core support for the maintenance of MIRRI coordinating nodes domiciled in their country, invest in enhancement of national mBRCs as well as contributing a fixed contribution to the MIRRI-ERIC. By introducing National Nodes the nations' mBRCs can be coordinated to address national priorities and operated more efficiently and on a more cost effective basis. The national nodes can be simple coordinating centres where they are a conduit to bring ideas and activities together or they can take on central functions and additional services and holdings to be decided upon in a coordinated approach. The level of support for nodes will depend upon the extent of their functions within MIRRI and subsequently upon the services that they provide. Although MIRRI will set participatory requirements on individual mBRCs and National Nodes it is expected that individual Member States may make rather distinctive arrangements with mBRCs within their jurisdictions so that they may function within MIRRI.

The MIRRI-ERIC Statutes requires a National Coordinator be appointed in each Member State that signs the MIRRI-ERIC to deliver the coordination of national mBRCs and linking out to research collections at all levels in the country. Additional costs would be office rental, travel, subsistence and other costs assuming 4 MIRRI-ERIC-meetings, in-country travel, an International Stakeholder Forum, National Stakeholder Forum plus a network meeting each year, costs for public relations, printing, Internet presence and running costs. The average cost of establishing a national node is estimated at just over €1 million over the first 5 years.

FINANCE MODELS FOR mBRCs

MIRRI aims to support mBRCs to become sustainable and outlines here some of the many financial models currently in operation across the microbial resource collections world. Recent studies by the OECD and the EMbaRC project have summarised some of the working models of mBRCs⁽¹⁵⁾. The most common is a fee for service and product base supported by host institutional or governmental support. Generally, funding is limited and it is often the case that where it is provided it is often balanced against the income received for the various services and products offered by the collection and in many cases the additional income above plan is returned to the funder. Where budgets are so finely balanced there is very little financial support for collection development to enable the collections to improve their coverage and incorporate new and advancing technologies. There are few collections that are self-financing but they are able to remain sustainable through a variety of routes. The mBRC or its host may have opportunities for other types of cost recovery activities and these often revolve around expertise and facilities available. The degree to which such activities may actually provide support sufficient to ensure financial sustainability of an mBRC is unproven. Other kinds of funding sources include support from industry, grants from agencies that support research,

15 Smith, D., Mc Cluskey, K. & Stackebrandt, E. (2014). Culture Collection funding models and BRC business plans, SpringerPlus 3, 81. <http://www.springerplus.com/content/3/1/81>

development of databases and other tools that complement the core role of mBRCs. Even funding from charitable sources, especially those associated with public health or sustainable development are sources of support. Evaluating different funding mechanisms is a core part of the MIRRI activities. Despite there not being one model for their operational and financial sustainability we can learn a lot from the experience of existing culture collections. It is difficult to estimate these costs as they vary so much dependent upon the difficulty in handling and preserving some microorganisms and the extent to which the biological material is characterised. The costs of the day to day running of the mBRC are to be met by the mBRCs themselves and it is the additional costs needed to establish local MIRRI activities and meet MIRRI standards that the MIRRI Financial Plan is looking to cover.

MIRRI will assist its participant collections to introduce the most appropriate business plans and ensure best value for money. It is evident that both the mBRCs and the MIRRI infrastructure require support funding and they must be balanced funding one at the expense of the other would not work.

INCOME GENERATION

Financial contributions are anticipated from the Members to fund the MIRRI-ERIC. The level of financial contributions of the Members (including a minimum annual monetary contribution) is to be determined by the General Assembly. Figure 14 shows the flow of finances through the MIRRI-ERIC and MIRRI infrastructure. These can be made through monetary contributions and in-kind contributions in the form of operating and/or capital contributions subject to payment of the minimum annual monetary contribution. The General Assembly will establish an accounting system and will develop rules for the acceptance of in-kind contributions and the assessment of their value. The contribution is calculated based on GDP per capita, and a fixed rate applicable to all. Annex IV shows the currently estimated costs split for specific countries with Germany contributing around €235K rising with inflation as its contribution and other Member States to a lesser extent.

FIGURE 14. FLOW OF FINANCES MIRRI-ERIC AND MIRRI RI

Additionally, funding will be sought from funded projects or revenue generation from services provided by the Central Coordinating Unit. This may include licensing of any applicable intellectual property rights (IPRs). As such income grows the costs to Member States will reduce. Any further revenue generated through MIRRI-ERIC via centrally coordinated activities will be retained by MIRRI and spent on such matters as are decided by the General Assembly thus reducing costs further to Member States.

A coordinated approach will lead to efficiencies and savings for example by discontinuation of specific holdings in those mBRCs that are not bound to mandates, outsourcing of identification, technology and expertise sharing.

Third party grants would rise over the years to around 30% of income with additional contributions coming from the CCU's Host Member State, access fees and membership fees. Following the initial investments to upgrade national mBRCs to function as National Nodes governmental costs would focus on support of the day-to-day operations of nodes and participating mBRCs. However, change in direction of some of the spend of this funding would be anticipated; currently there is little available for improvement of services and keeping pace with technology it is envisaged that due to increased efficiencies and shared activity cost across the research infrastructure funds would be available for introduction of new technologies and additional expertise needed to develop new and innovative services and products. Additional targeted public expenditures may also be appropriate to ensure mBRCs make optimal contributions to the Member State-level bio-economy.

Table 4.2 shows in percentage terms how we see the necessary revenue being generated. It can be seen that it is anticipated that investment by Member States in financing the MIRRI-ERIC will reduce from 75% in year one to 50% cover of costs in year 5.

FUNDING SOURCE	FUNDING LEVEL (PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL COST)				
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5 **
Member States (6 signatories)	75	63	58	55	50
Third Party Grants	12.5	25	35	35	35
Coordinating hub host country	12.5	10	2	2	2
Bioindustry	0	1	3	4,5	8
mBRC membership fees	0	1	2	3,5	5
TOTAL	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

** Funding will be more or stable in years 6-10

TABLE 4.2 MIRRI-ERIC FUNDING INVESTMENT MODEL SHOWING PERCENTAGE SPLIT BETWEEN THE DIFFERENT SOURCES

It is anticipated that 5 countries would join MIRRI-ERIC in its first year; these countries and their percentage contributions based on average GDP could be Germany (31.28%), France (23.54%), Spain (11.69%), Belgium (4.37%) and the United Kingdom (21.70%) see figure 15. In this calculation, The Netherlands and Italy would join as Observers.

FIGURE 15. MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS BASED ON AVERAGE GDP IN YEAR 1

In year 10 the MIRRI-ERIC would be signed by more countries and others will have joined as observers. The costs although rising for inflation would be shared and reduce the contributions of the original 5 countries. If we anticipate 10 Member States and 3 Observer States then the split would be as shown in figure 16.

FIGURE 16. MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS BASED ON AVERAGE GDP IN YEAR 5

It is essential that all possible sources of funding be explored for the long-term functioning of the infrastructure and for the envisioned improved access to resources and services.

WHAT NEEDS TO HAPPEN NOW

The Preparatory Phase will establish the statutes and documentation necessary for the establishment of the MIRRI-ERIC. Currently it is difficult at this stage to estimate the exact number of Member States that will participate. The commitment to MIRRI has mainly been expressed through the mBRCs themselves but many have some national government support in this. In placing MIRRI on the ESFRI road map state representatives expressed their full support but with no commitment to fund. It is a key priority to engage with States and secure financial commitment for its future development and operation. To get this commitment in the first instance countries are being invited to sign up to the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Third Iteration of the Business Plan presenting key information to help them make that commitment. To date Belgium, Germany, France, Czech Republic, Portugal, Poland and Russia have shown an interest with the remaining full partner countries of Italy, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, UK being asked initially to sign up to the MoU; representing 12 countries. The MIRRI-ERIC critical mass is considered 5 Member States to be financially viable. It will take time to reach this level of participation and it is anticipated that there will be an interim phase between the Preparatory Phase ending and the implementation of MIRRI. Currently drafts of the four documents needed to implement the MIRRI-ERIC are underway and final versions of these will be needed in the short-term.

THE INTERIM PHASE

Interim measures will need to be put in place prior to the signing of the MIRRI-ERIC. To date, it is envisaged that interested Member States will sign a MoU and subsequently be invited to join an Interim Governing Board. The National Nodes would keep their own legal status within states. Interested Member States will be invited to send one technical and one administrative delegate each to the Interim Board.

It is envisaged that a Scientific Advisory Board would be established by the Interim Board – which subsequently could be validated by the Full Board. The duties of the Scientific Advisory Board are yet to be fully determined but would include support on strategy, work programme design (see figure 9) and operational issues; they would review proposals for further development of the infrastructure and proposals for new members. The Scientific Advisory Board would ensure user benefits are delivered from the improved quality management of mBRCs delivering a consistent level of service and better access to authentic and reproducible materials in a transparent and traceable way.

It is clear that there will be a gap in funding between the Preparatory Phase and the implementation of MIRRI (signing of the MIRRI-ERIC). The key partners have demonstrated in the past their commitment to such purposes, for example the continuation of the CABRI activities from project closure to date. The Steering Committee have some institutional support to continue work during this period to keep the process on track. As soon as the minimum number of signatories (5) a Kick-Off Meeting for the Implementation Phase and first meeting of the Governing Board will be organised.

The governance structure during the Operational Phase will be an extension of that created in the Implementation Phase adapting as more participants join to ensure representation but keeping a manageable number of decision makers. MIRRI is quite lucky as there are numerous RIs that go before it that it can benefit from the experience of; MIRRI will work with these RIs and the stakeholders to ensure a sound mechanism.

MIRRI must accelerate its development process. Annexe I provides a list of the Preparatory Phase work packages (WP) that build the structure and define its outputs. It is clear that the strategies and infrastructure design from WP 2 'Design of the Microbial Resource Research distributed Infrastructure' and WP 3 'Define governance structure, legal status and operational practice' are key to delivering the final version of this Business Plan and its financial implications. All work packages are designed to improve the intrinsic strength of MIRRI mBRCs.

STRATEGY FOR ENGAGEMENT OF NATIONAL FUNDERS

Partners are requested to continue discussions with the most appropriate government contacts using the MIRRI Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and this iteration of the Business Plan and report back. Partners should select the appropriate representatives from the lists of ESFRI delegates and country Research Infrastructure Committee representatives. Alternatively, Partners may already have direct contact with the relevant government department and this contact should be the starting point for engagement. MIRRI partners will report back on outcomes, WP4 task leaders and the Steering Committee will collate the feedback and share lessons learned with partners. MIRRI preparatory phase partners should engage their ministries and main funders in reviewing the MIRRI-ERIC documentation and design to ensure they develop in the right way.

ANTICIPATED OUTCOMES AND IMPACT:

Placement of MIRRI on national roadmaps: national representative signature to the MoU will signal national commitment which is the first step to an ERIC.

STEPS IN ESTABLISHING MIRRI

- » engage users, mBRCs, governments and funders with Business Plan, draft Statutes, Partner Charter and Rules of Operation
- » signature on MoU or letter in support of the principles of MIRRI
- » set up interim Governing Board with participation of Member States expressing interest
- » expand MIRRI's Advisory Board to include representation of the research and industrial communities being served by MIRRI
- » establish Interim Governing Board (currently the EC Preparatory Phase contracted Coordinator supported by the Steering Committee)
- » utilise the MIRRI Preparatory Phase secretariat to establish the central hub; a process for selection of future central hub will be designed and implemented
- » test the managerial conduits to direct the secretariat, National Nodes and mBRC participants in delivering MIRRI outputs and finalise governance structure
- » establish/select an interim legal entity to allow MIRRI to operate in the run-up to enough ERIC signatures to formally create MIRRI as an independent body.
- » seek commitments to funding
- » establish MIRRI-ERIC when a critical mass of 5 nations sign up to the MoU and at least 10 mBRCs have reached the BRC standard for participation

TIMEFRAME FOR DELIVERY OF MIRRI

ACTIVITY	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Engage users					
Signature of MoU or letter of support					
Set up interim Governing Board					
Expand MIRRI's Advisory Board					
Establish the CCU					
Test the managerial conduits					
Finalise Governance structure					
Establish interim legal entity					
Seek commitments to funding					
Interim Phase					
Establish the MIRRI-ERIC					
Establish MIRRI: Operational phase					

IN SUMMARY: WHY SHOULD GOVERNMENTS SUPPORT MIRRI?

Delivery of high quality microbial resources with facilities to data mine associated data sets will facilitate research and accelerate the discovery of new products and stimulate innovative microbial solutions to the Grand Challenges. MIRRI will facilitate this by ensuring interoperability between microbial strain data and other relevant data sets such as DNA and protein sequences, ecological data, metabolites, geographical data and phylogenetic relationships. MIRRI will deliver a coordinated accession policy to broaden coverage of resources, increase capacity to store and deliver more characterised microorganisms to researchers.

The MIRRI-ERIC will include a proportion of user access to facilities, services and resources; a commitment to take deposits identified in the MIRRI common accession policy and participation in the expert clusters. mBRC participation in the MIRRI National Nodes will be governed by commitments made in the Partner Charter which will include delivery of high quality data to agreed standards, participation in capacity building programmes and a commitment to deliver the MIRRI communication and outreach strategy to stakeholders particularly to bio-industry.

This will enhance knowledge underpinning research and education, deliver efficiency and cost effectiveness in the management of microbial resources and protect the investment in publicly funded research. The long-term access to the biological materials on which the science is based will enable confirmation of results and further work facilitating high quality research and good science. The Research Infrastructure will support academic and industrial research with high quality services and material. The societal impact will be to improve the economy and create employment through the biotechnological discoveries in healthcare, food security and livelihoods that MIRRI will underpin.

ANNEX

ANNEX I: WORK PACKAGES

The design of the MIRRI infrastructure and its work programmes and activities is being taken forward through a series of interrelated work packages (WP).

WP 1 MIRRI preparatory phase project management

WP 2 Design of the Microbial Resource Research distributed Infrastructure

WP 3 Define governance structure, legal status and operational practice

WP 4 Financial plan

WP 5 Communication, dissemination and outreach

WP 6 Development of services, outputs and foster interdisciplinary work programs

WP 7 Capacity building, education and training

WP 8 Data resources management

WP 9 Legal operational framework for access to Microbial Resources

WP 10 Delivering innovation

The work packages address the key issues that have arisen in the design and development of other RIs.

It is imperative that all stakeholders are involved from an early stage, particularly the potential funders. Work package 5 identifies all the relevant stakeholders, provides a strategy for their engagement and coordinates these tasks across work packages assigning priorities, action plans and timelines. Partners will use the output of Work package 4, the business plan and engagement strategy to introduce MIRRI on their national roadmaps and in Operational Programmes for Structural Funds.

A key and early activity is the design of the legal and governance structure (Work package 3) with the supporting sustainable financial plan in order to reduce the lead time in solving legal and governance issues. Collaboration and outreach, the subject of Work package 5, as well as Work package 6, aim to develop the capacity for MIRRI to operate Transnational Access as a potential instrument to ensure the best use of available project funds dependent on the specific situation of the RI and its services.

MIRRI is aware of the need in its Preparatory Phase to develop measures to reduce legal and other barriers to cross border access to the resources of the distributed RI (Work package 9).

Work package 7 addresses capacity building, education and training both within the infrastructure to ensure an increasing set of expertise to deliver its products and services but to the outside also, in transnational access for users. The data resources management of MIRRI will be addressed by work package 8 ensuring user input in design of the information system to ensure user needs are properly addressed. An appropriate legal operational framework for access to microbial resources is essential and this must be compatible outside Europe, work package 9 will address key issues such as Access and Benefit Sharing through implementation of the Nagoya Protocol as well as biosecurity issues. All through the preparatory phase delivering innovative approaches will be at the forefront and work package 10 examines appropriate mechanisms for taking key ideas forward for delivery in the implementation and operational phases.

ANNEX II: MIRRI ADVISORY BOARD

The chair of the Advisory Board is Professor Iain Gillespie, University of Edinburgh and he will take up the role of Director of Science, National Environmental Research Council, UK. Previously he was Head of the Science and Technology Policy Division of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), prior to that head of the OECD's Biotechnology Division (2001-2011) and he led the OECD BRC initiative and helped to design the OECD approach to the Bioeconomy. He is ably supported by Professor Indrikis Muiznieks, Professor of Microbiology and Immunology at the University of Latvia a full Member of the Latvian Academy of Sciences, Head of the Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology and Vice-rector for Research, Latvia; Dame Janet Thornton, Director of the European Bioinformatics Institute on the Wellcome, Trust Genome Campus at Hinxton, UK; Director of the Centre of Competence AGROINNOVA and Vice-Rector for International Affairs and President of the International Society for Plant Pathology (ISPP), Italy; and Daniel Ramon, Biopolis SL as Chief Scientific Officer, previously Professor at the Institute of Agrochemistry and Food Technology of the National Spanish Research Council, and prior to that Professor of Food Technology at the University of Valencia, Spain.

ANNEX III: GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Member: EU-Member States, associated countries, third countries or intergovernmental organizations that sign the MIRRI-ERIC as members and make a full contribution to the MIRRI budget.

Observer: EU-Member States, associated countries, third countries or intergovernmental organizations that are in the process of developing appropriate partner facilities or that want to be involved in joint projects with specific scope and time perspective. They sign the MIRRI-ERIC as observers and make a partial contribution to the MIRRI budget.

Partner: mBRC or institution providing resources or services or participating in joint projects in the frame of MIRRI.

National Node: Operational body present in each MIRRI Member State that coordinates the activities of the partners within the country, organises funding, provides or advises in training issues, enhances the development of the national mBRCs as well as expands the national network to improve the offer.

ABBREVIATIONS

BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
BRC	Biological Resource Centre
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
DSMZ	Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganism and Cell Cultures
ECDC	European Centre of Disease and Prevention Control
ECCO	European Culture Collections' Organisation
ELIXIR	European Life Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
EMbaRC	European Consortium of Microbial Resource Centres
EMBRC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERINHA	European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU-OPENSREEN	European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology
GBRCN	Global Biological Resource Centre Network
INSTRUCT	Integrated Structural Biology Infrastructure for Europe
K	1.000
MIRRI	Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding

mBRC	microbial domain Biological Resource Centre
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
QBOL	Quarantine Barcode of Life
QMS	Quality Management System
RI	Research Infrastructure
WFCC	World Federation for Culture Collections
WP	Work Package
y	year

ANNEX IV: FINANCIAL TABLES FOR MIRRI

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Employee	National Coordinator	107,950.00 €	111,188.50 €	114,524.16 €	117,959.88 €	121,498.68 €	573,121.21 €
Office	Rental	12,000.00 €	12,900.00 €	13,867.50 €	14,907.56 €	16,025.63 €	69,700.69 €
Travel	4 MIRRI-ERIC-meetings, national travels, international Stakeholder Forum	40,000.00 €	43,000.00 €	46,225.00 €	49,691.88 €	53,418.77 €	232,335.64 €
National Stakeholder Forum	1 meeting/year	15,000.00 €	16,125.00 €	17,334.38 €	18,634.45 €	20,032.04 €	87,125.87 €
Public relation	printing, Internet	8,000.00 €	8,600.00 €	9,245.00 €	9,938.38 €	10,683.75 €	46,467.13 €
running costs	e.g. communication, reports (€ 2000/year)	5,000.00 €	5,375.00 €	5,778.13 €	6,211.48 €	6,677.35 €	29,041.96 €
TOTAL costs NN		187,950.00 €	197,188.50 €	206,974.16 €	217,343.63 €	228,336.21 €	1,037,792.49 €

TABLE 1. NATIONAL COSTS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A NATIONAL NODE WITHIN MIRRI-ERIC

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Implementation of OECD Best Practice Guidelines	QM System	12,000.00 €	12,900.00 €	13,867.50 €	14,907.56 €	16,025.63 €	69,700.69 €
	Annual costs QM System	8,000.00 €	8,600.00 €	9,245.00 €	9,938.38 €	10,683.75 €	46,467.13 €
Technology development	Equipment for preservation and characterisation	30,000.00 €	32,250.00 €	34,668.75 €	37,268.91 €	40,064.07 €	174,251.73 €
mBRC expertise	Training and exchange of 4 scientists	20,000.00 €	21,500.00 €	23,112.50 €	24,845.94 €	26,709.38 €	116,167.82 €
Acquisition	10% additional uptake (€385/strain), 200 strains in 5-year frame	15,400.00 €	16,555.00 €	17,796.63 €	19,131.37 €	20,566.22 €	89,449.22 €
Expert platform	participation of scientists	4,000.00 €	4,300.00 €	4,622.50 €	4,969.19 €	5,341.88 €	23,233.56 €
Access to facilities and techniques	Access costs for 20 % of visitors, at least four stays, €4,000/visits	16,000.00 €	17,200.00 €	18,490.00 €	19,876.75 €	21,367.51 €	92,934.26 €
TOTAL cost		105,400.00 €	113,305.00 €	121,802.88 €	130,938.09 €	140,758.45 €	612,204.41 €

TABLE 2 NATIONAL COSTS FOR UPGRADING A mBRC WITHIN MIRRI-ERIC

MEMBER/ OBSERVER*	AV. GDP [MIO US \$]	% GDP	BASE CONTRI- BUTION [€]	VARIABLE SHARE [€]	TOTAL CONTRI- BUTION [€]	SHARE OF TOTAL CONTRIBUTION
Belgium	508,116	4.37%	25,000 €	19,871 €	44,871 €	4.37%
Spain	1,358,263	11.69%	35,000 €	84,947 €	119,947 €	11.69%
United Kingdom	2,521,381	21.70%	45,000 €	177,660 €	222,660 €	21.70%
France	2,734,949	23.54%	45,000 €	196,520 €	241,520 €	23.54%
Germany	3,634,823	31.28%	45,000 €	275,987 €	320,987 €	31.28%
Netherlands*	240,052	2.07%	7,500 €	13,699 €	21,199 €	2.07%
Italy*	621,392	5.35%	13,500 €	41,374 €	54,874 €	5.35%
TOTALS	11,618,976	100.00%	216,000 €	810,058 €	1,026,058 €	100%

TABLE 3. YEAR 1 MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE MIRRI-ERIC BASED ON GDP IF 5 COUNTRIES JOIN MIRRI WITH 2 OBSERVERS (*)

MEMBER/ OBSERVER*	AV. GDP [MIO US \$]	% GDP	BASE CONTRI- BUTION [€]	VARIABLE SHARE [€]	TOTAL CONTRI- BUTION [€]	SHARE OF TOTAL CONTRIBUTION
Belgium	508,116	3.95%	25,000 €	15,564 €	40,564 €	3.95%
Netherlands	800,173	6.23%	25,000 €	38,879 €	63,879 €	6.23%
Spain	1,358,263	10.57%	35,000 €	73,432 €	108,432 €	10.57%
United Kingdom	2,521,381	19.62%	45,000 €	156,286 €	201,286 €	19.62%
France	2,734,949	21.28%	45,000 €	173,335 €	218,335 €	21.28%
Germany	3,634,823	28.28%	45,000 €	245,173 €	290,173 €	28.28%
Italy*	621,392	4.83%	13,500 €	36,107 €	49,607 €	4.83%
Brazil*	673,702	5.24%	13,500 €	40,283 €	53,783 €	5.24%
TOTALS	12,852,799	100.00%	247,000 €	779,058 €	1,026,058 €	100.00%

TABLE 4. YEAR 2 MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE MIRRI-ERIC BASED ON GDP WITH 6 COUNTRIES JOIN MIRRI WITH 2 OBSERVERS (*)

MEMBER/ OBSERVER*	AV. GDP [MIO US \$]	% GDP	BASE CONTRI- BUTION [€]	VARIABLE SHARE [€]	TOTAL CONTRI- BUTION [€]	SHARE OF TOTAL CONTRIBUTION
Portugal	220,022	1.59%	25,000 €	0 €	25,000 €	2.21%
Belgium	508,116	3.67%	25,000 €	12,646 €	37,646 €	3.33%
Netherlands	800,173	5.78%	25,000 €	34,284 €	59,284 €	5.24%
Spain	1,358,263	9.81%	35,000 €	65,632 €	100,632 €	8.90%
Italy	2,071,307	14.96%	45,000 €	108,461 €	153,461 €	13.57%
United Kingdom	2,521,381	18.21%	45,000 €	141,806 €	186,806 €	16.51%
France	2,734,949	19.75%	45,000 €	157,629 €	202,629 €	17.91%
Germany	3,634,823	26.25%	45,000 €	224,300 €	269,300 €	23.80%
Russian Federation*	629,033	4.54%	13,500 €	33,104 €	46,604 €	4.12%
Brazil*	673,702	4.86%	13,500 €	36,414 €	49,914 €	4.41%
TOTALS	13,849,034	100.00%	317,000 €	814,275 €	1,131,275 €	100.00%

TABLE 5. YEAR 5 MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE MIRRI-ERIC BASED ON GDP WITH 8 MEMBER STATES AND 2 OBSERVERS (*)

ANNEX IV: FINANCIAL TABLES FOR MIRRI

MEMBER/ OBSERVER*	AV. GDP [MIO US \$]	% GDP	BASE CONTRI- BUTION [€]	VARIABLE SHARE [€]	TOTAL CONTRI- BUTION [€]	SHARE OF TOTAL CONTRIBUTION
Portugal	220,022	1.32%	25,000 €	0 €	25,000 €	2.32%
Belgium	508,116	3.06%	25,000 €	6,384 €	31,384 €	2.91%
Poland	517,543	3.12%	25,000 €	6,966 €	31,966 €	2.96%
Netherlands	800,173	4.82%	25,000 €	24,423 €	49,423 €	4.58%
Spain	1,358,263	8.18%	35,000 €	48,893 €	83,893 €	7.77%
Italy	2,071,307	12.47%	45,000 €	82,935 €	127,935 €	11.85%
Brazil	2,245,673	13.52%	45,000 €	93,704 €	138,704 €	12.85%
United Kingdom	2,521,381	15.18%	45,000 €	110,733 €	155,733 €	14.42%
France	2,734,949	16.46%	45,000 €	123,925 €	168,925 €	15.64%
Germany	3,634,823	21.88%	45,000 €	179,505 €	224,505 €	20.79%
Kenya*	13,230	0.08%	7,500 €	0 €	7,500 €	0.69%
India*	563,039	3.39%	10,500 €	24,276 €	34,776 €	3.22%
TOTALS	16,612,250	100.00%	378,000 €	701,744 €	1,079,744 €	100.00%

TABLE 6. YEAR 6 MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE MIRRI-ERIC BASED ON GDP WITH 10 MEMBER STATES AND 2 OBSERVERS (*)

MEMBER/ OBSERVER*	AV. GDP [MIO US \$]	% GDP	BASE CONTRI- BUTION [€]	VARIABLE SHARE [€]	TOTAL CONTRI- BUTION [€]	SHARE OF TOTAL CONTRIBUTION
Portugal	220,022	1.32%	25,000 €	0 €	25,000 €	2.30%
Belgium	508,116	3.06%	25,000 €	6,384 €	31,384 €	2.89%
Poland	517,543	3.12%	25,000 €	6,966 €	31,966 €	2.94%
Netherlands	800,173	4.82%	25,000 €	24,423 €	49,423 €	4.55%
Spain	1,358,263	8.18%	35,000 €	48,893 €	83,893 €	7.72%
Italy	2,071,307	12.47%	45,000 €	82,935 €	127,935 €	11.77%
Brazil	2,245,673	13.52%	45,000 €	93,704 €	138,704 €	12.76%
United Kingdom	2,521,381	15.18%	45,000 €	110,733 €	155,733 €	14.32%
France	2,734,949	16.46%	45,000 €	123,925 €	168,925 €	15.54%
Germany	3,634,823	21.88%	45,000 €	179,505 €	224,505 €	20.65%
Kenya*	13,230	0.08%	7,500 €	0 €	7,500 €	0.69%
Denmark*	99,184	0.60%	7,500 €	0 €	7,500 €	0.69%
India*	563,039	3.39%	10,500 €	24,276 €	34,776 €	3.20%
TOTALS	16,612,250	100.00%	385,500 €	701,744 €	1,087,244 €	100.00%

TABLE 7. YEAR 5 MEMBER STATE CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE MIRRI-ERIC BASED ON GDP WITH 10 MEMBER STATES AND 3 OBSERVERS (*)

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Elected mBRC Head	National Coordinator	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Employee (part time)	Executive Secretary	12,000.00 €	12,900.00 €	13867.50 €	14907.56 €	16025.63 €	69,700.69 €
Office at UK mBRC	Rental	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Travel	4 MIRRI-ERIC-meetings, national travels, international Stakeholder Forum	10,000.00 €	10,750.00 €	11,556.25 €	12,422.97 €	13,354.69 €	58,083.91 €
National Stakeholder Forum	1 meeting/year	15,000.00 €	16,125.00 €	17,334.38 €	18,634.45 €	20,032.04 €	87,125.87 €
Public relation	printing, Internet	8,000.00 €	8,600.00 €	9,245.00 €	9,938.38 €	10,683.75 €	46,467.13 €
Running costs	e.g. communication,	2,000.00 €	2,150.00 €	2,310.00 €	2485.00 €	2671.00 €	11,616.00 €
TOTAL costs NN		47,000 €	50,525 €	54,313 €	58,388 €	62,767 €	272,993.60 €

TABLE 8 COSTS FOR ESTABLISHMENT OF A UK NATIONAL NODE BASED ON THE UKBRCN

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Implementation of OECD Best Practice Guidelines	QM System	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
	Annual costs QM System	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Technology development	Equipment for preservation and characterisation	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
mBRC expertise	Training and exchange of 4 scientists	20,000.00 €	21,500.00 €	23,112.50 €	24,845.94 €	26,709.38 €	116,167.82 €
Acquisition	10% additional uptake (€385/strain), 200 strains in 5-year frame	15,400.00 €	16,555.00 €	17,796.63 €	19,131.37 €	20,566.22 €	89,449.22 €
Expert platform	participation of scientists	4,000.00 €	4,300.00 €	4,622.50 €	4,969.19 €	5,341.88 €	23,233.57 €
Access to facilities and techniques	Access costs for 20% of visitors, at least four stays, € 4.000/visits	16,000.00 €	17,200.00 €	18,490.00 €	19,876.75 €	21,367.51 €	92,934.26 €
TOTAL cost		55,400.00 €	59,555.00 €	64,021.63 €	68,823.25 €	73,984.99 €	321,784.87 €

TABLE 9 UK COSTS FOR UPGRADING A mBRC WITHIN MIRRI-ERIC

ANNEX IV: FINANCIAL TABLES FOR MIRRI

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Employer	National Coordinator	107,950.00 €	111,188.50 €	114,524.16 €	117,959.88 €	121,498.68 €	573,121.21 €
Office	rental	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
Travel	4 MIRRI-ERIC-Meetings, national travels, International Stakeholder Forum	40,000.00 €	43,000.00 €	46,225.00 €	49,691.88 €	53,418.77 €	232,335.64 €
National Stakeholder Forum	1 meeting/year	10,000.00 €	10,750.00 €	11,556.25 €	12,422.97 €	13,354.69 €	58,083.91 €
Public relation	printing, Internet	3,000.00 €	3,225.00 €	3,466.88 €	3,726.89 €	4,006.41 €	17,425.17 €
Running cost	e.g. communication, reports (€2000/year)	5,000.00 €	5,375.00 €	5,778.13 €	6,211.48 €	6,677.35 €	29,041.96 €
TOTAL costs NN		165,950.00 €	173,538.50 €	181,550.41 €	190,013.10 €	198,955.89 €	910,007.89 €

TABLE 10. GERMAN NATIONAL COSTS FOR NN IM MIRRI-ERIC

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Implementation OECD Best Practice Guidelines	QM System	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
	Annual costs QM System	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
Technology development	Equipment for preservation and characterisation	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
mBRC Expertise	Training and exchange of scientists für 4 persons	20,000.00 €	21,500.00 €	23,112.50 €	24,845.94 €	26,709.38 €	116,167.82 €
Acquisition	10% additional uptake (€385/strain), 200 strains within 5-year frame	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
Expert platform	Participation of scientists	4,000.00 €	4,300.00 €	4,622.50 €	4,969.19 €	5,341.88 €	23,233.56 €
Access to facilities and techniques	Access costs for 20 % of visitors, at least four stays, €4.000/visits	16,000.00 €	16,120.00 €	16,240.90 €	16,362.71 €	16,485.43 €	81,209.03 €
TOTAL costs mBRC		40,000.00 €	41,920.00 €	43,975.90 €	46,177.83 €	48,536.69 €	220,610.42 €

TABLE 12. GERMAN NATIONAL COSTS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A mBRC IM MIRRI-ERIC

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Employee	2 lawyers	203,200.00 €	210,312.00 €	217,672.92 €	225,291.47 €	233,176.67 €	1,089,653.07 €
Travel and accomodation	Diverse meetings, material	15,000.00 €	16,125.00 €	17,334.38 €	18,634.45 €	20,032.04 €	87,125.87 €
TOTAL costs Nagoya		218,200.00 €	226,437.00 €	235,007.30 €	243,925.93 €	253,208.71 €	1,176,778.93 €

TABLE 13. COSTS CENTRAL POSITION FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF NAGOYA PROTOKOL WITHIN DSMZ

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS YEAR 1*	COSTS YEAR 2*	COSTS YEAR 3*	COSTS YEAR 4*	COSTS YEAR 5*	TOTAL COSTS YEAR 1-5
Office	rental, equipment for 5 persons (75m ² at 12€/m ² /month)	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
Consumables	Consumables and communication €7.000/year	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
Public relation and Outreach	prints, posters, fair, booth, registration fees	40,000.00 €	43,000.00 €	46,225.00 €	49,691.88 €	53,418.77 €	232,335.64 €
Annual meeting, Stakeholder meeting	1 annual meeting; 1 Stakeholder meeting/year	100,000.00 €	107,500.00 €	115,562.50 €	124,229.69 €	133,546.91 €	580,839.10 €
TOTAL costs Infrastructure CCU - host country		140,000.00 €	150,500.00 €	161,787.50 €	173,921.56 €	186,965.68 €	813,174.74 €

TABLE 14. HOST COUNTRY COSTS (EXAMPLE GERMANY)

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS / YEAR 5 MIRRI-MEMBER	COSTS / YEAR 10 MIRRI-MEMBER
National Node	National costs for the establishment of a National Node in MIRRI-ERIC	165,950.00 €	165,950.00 €
mBRC	National costs for the establishment of a mBRC in MIRRI-ERIC	40,000.00 €	40,000.00 €
Nagoya-node	Cost for establishment of implementation of Nagoya Protocol	218,200.00 €	218,200.00 €
CCU	Host country costs for CCU	140,000.00 €	140,000.00 €
Membership	Membership contribution for MIRRI-ERIC	320,986.90 €	224,505.36 €
TOTAL		885,136.90 €	788,655.36 €

TABLE 15. TOTAL COSTS GERMANY FOR PARTICIPATION IN MIRRI-ERIC

ITEM	DETAILS	COSTS / YEAR
National Node	National costs for the establishment of a National Node in MIRRI-ERIC	22,000.00 €
mBRC	National costs for the establishment of a mBRC in MIRRI-ERIC	65,400.00 €
Nagoya-node	Cost for establishment of implementation of Nagoya Protokol	- €
CCU	Host country costs for CCU	31,000.00 €
membership fee	Membership contribution for MIRRI-ERIC	- €
TOTAL		118,400.00 €

TABLE 16. SAVINGS ON TOTAL COSTS FOR GERMANY IF DSMZ IS SELECTED AS SEAT OF CCU AND AS NATIONAL NODE

COORDINATION & CONTACT

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SEVENTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME
SP4-Capacities
Combination of CP & CSA

PREPARATORY PHASES
FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1
Grant Agreement Number: 312251